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Blue Carbon in India – Opportunities informed by the most recent science

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Restored mangroves in Pichavaram Mangrove Forest, Tamil Nadu (credit: Elina Apine)

Executive Summary

The intent of this report, commissioned by the Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO), is to outline the current state of blue carbon research and policy within India to generate evidence needs statements and understand the direction of future research where there is scope for collaboration and partnership working. Research collaboration in discovery science is an important aspect of UK-India partnership. In the context of policy opportunities for blue carbon ecosystems to deliver climate change mitigation and adaptation, this partnership offers an opportunity for UK researchers to contribute their expertise and experience to the development of successful science-based policy initiatives in India. This is an emerging opportunity for both the UK and India to develop a joint programme of work in a novel and nature-positive field of ocean science research which can contribute to the wider goals of the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030).

Blue carbon refers to the carbon stored in coastal marine ecosystems, specifically mangroves, saltmarshes, and seagrasses. While the term blue carbon largely focuses on the climate change mitigation potential of these ecosystems, these ecosystems also have great potential as nature-based solutions providing benefits for climate, people and biodiversity. All three blue carbon ecosystems are present along India's ~7,500-kilometre coastline. India holds around 3% of the world's mangrove forests, but the extent of saltmarshes and seagrasses are much less certain. While there has been a significant output of research in the past several years on Indian blue carbon, there is still a great need for more evidence to support policy and investment in blue carbon ecosystem conservation and restoration, particularly within saltmarshes and seagrasses which remain understudied. India therefore presents a great wealth of natural capital opportunities in which nature markets, such as those being developed in the UK, could be translated and applied with significant benefit to India's coastal ecosystems, people and blue economy.

The report thus addresses the following questions:

Question 1: What is the current state of blue carbon research and policy within India?

Question 2: Where are the significant gaps within the scientific and grey literature?

Question 3: How can the identified gaps be filled to create a cohesive picture to inform policymaking?

A rigorous literature review was conducted incorporating 180 peer-reviewed articles containing the search term “blue carbon” in India. This review revealed that while there is an extensive literature on mangrove forests, there is still limited understanding of the distribution and blue carbon potential of India’s seagrasses and saltmarshes. A policy scan was conducted to review international frameworks and national and state policies and legislation that relate to blue carbon ecosystems. This included 102 international, national and state level policies and legislation. The role of mangroves in increasing resilience and supporting livelihoods was recognised, but the mitigation potential of blue carbon ecosystems is not yet fully acknowledged.

Based on the outcomes of this literature review and policy scan, seven gaps have been identified as areas for further work.

Gap 1 – Habitat Mapping: While mangrove ecosystems are well surveyed in India, there is limited data available on the distribution of seagrass meadows and saltmarshes, and even less data regarding their health and blue carbon potential.

Gap 2 – Blue Carbon Mitigation Potential: The benefits of mangrove habitats, in particular, are recognised in India for biodiversity and climate change adaptation. However, the climate change mitigation potential of all blue carbon ecosystems is not fully recognised in national and state policies and legislation.

Gap 3 – Measurement Methodologies: There is a wealth of valuable blue carbon data available in India. In order to generate accurate measurements of carbon stocks, a consistent methodology is required, which includes standardised methods in line with IPCC requirements, as well as methods to bring existing stock data in line with these reporting requirements.

Gap 4 – Blue Carbon Stock Take: Carbon stocks, greenhouse gas emissions, and related blue carbon assessment data are increasingly available for mangroves, however these data are incomplete for saltmarshes and seagrasses. There is also limited data on total (aboveground, belowground and soil) carbon stocks for all blue carbon ecosystems across India.

Gap 5 – Impacts of Climate Change: There is a growing understanding of the significance of climate change across India, however limited attention has been given to these impacts (including sea level rise, drought, etc.) on blue carbon potential.

Gap 6 – Geographical Distribution of Research: The spatial coverage of blue carbon research across India is growing, but this research is concentrated in a few highly studied regions (e.g., the Sundarbans and Bhitarkanika) and does not expand equally to other blue-carbon rich areas.

Gap 7 – Restoration and Monitoring: There has been significant interest in mangrove conservation and restoration, but there is still limited focus on seagrass and saltmarsh habitat restoration and monitoring.

Gaps in blue carbon science and policy identified in this review.

Based on the gaps identified above, the following evidence needs have been established. Each of these needs responds to either one or more of the gaps highlighted above and are organised in terms of timelines to delivery. In many cases, these evidence needs build on each other and some actions need to be completed before others can take place.

Evidence Need	Description	Responds to which gaps?
1	Habitat mapping to provide a country-wide understanding of blue carbon ecosystem extent.	Gap 1: Habitat Mapping Gap 2: Blue Carbon Mitigation Potential Gap 6: Research Distribution
2	Feasibility assessment for incorporating blue carbon ecosystems into federal and state policies.	Gap 2: Blue Carbon Mitigation Potential
3	Standardised methods and quality control to allow for direct comparison of stocks across India, and to align Indian blue carbon stock measurements with global values.	Gap 3: Measurement Methodologies Gap 4: Blue Carbon Stock Take
4	Country-wide carbon stock (aboveground, belowground, and soil) assessments for mangrove, seagrass and saltmarsh habitats.	Gap 4: Blue Carbon Stock Take
5	Data on presence, health, and sequestration potential of blue carbon ecosystems in states where few publications have emerged (see Figure 10 in main text).	Gap 6: Research Distribution
6	Greater understanding of the impacts of climate change in blue carbon ecosystems to appropriately protect these ecosystems in the future.	Gap 5: Impacts of Climate Change
7	Greater understanding of how to effectively restore seagrass and saltmarsh habitats across different sites.	Gap 7: Restoration and Monitoring

The gap analysis and subsequent evidence needs have revealed potential opportunities for strengthening the role of blue carbon in the science and policy communities in India, including through partnership with the UK. However, further efforts would be needed to ensure that these solutions are equitable, practical, and implementable within the vastly different regions into which they might be put in place.

Opportunity Area 1 – A Collaborative Science Forum: Development of a country-wide programme that brings in expertise across the sectors, including earth scientists, ocean scientists, natural scientists, social scientists, policymakers, and community members, to develop a research protocol that responds to the science gaps identified in the report. *More details and actions are provided on page 51.*

Opportunity Area 2 – Development of a Blue Carbon Inventory for India informed by global efforts and ongoing work in the UK: Recent efforts in the UK to establish a national blue carbon roadmap and evidence needs partnerships could be adapted to an Indian context to support a nation-wide blue carbon stock take. An evidence needs partnership would aid the identification of evidence gaps beyond those identified in this report and develop methods to fill those gaps, by leveraging the expertise of all partners and shaping collaboration in a way that prioritises shared objectives. *More details and actions are provided on pages 51 and 52.*

Opportunity Area 3 – Weaving Blue Carbon Ecosystems into National and State Policies: This policy scan provides a great foundation for exploring how blue carbon could be further woven into national and state policies to achieve climate change mitigation, adaptation, and biodiversity benefits. Existing programmes such as the Mangrove Initiative for Shoreline Habitats and Tangible Income (MISHTI) and India Global Environment Facility Coastal and Marine Program (IGCMP) emphasise the importance of mangroves. However, saltmarshes and seagrass meadows remain largely neglected. These initiatives primarily focus on specific states such as Andhra Pradesh and West Bengal, highlighting the need for a national effort to support all states and union territories, especially those with more fragmented blue carbon habitats. Additionally, a shared government-to-government understanding of the opportunities of these policies on the ground is needed. *More details and actions are provided on page 52.*

Opportunity Area 4 – Emerging carbon and nature markets: Carbon markets could offer significant opportunities to finance blue carbon restoration projects, which often lack support from other funding sources. Organisations such as the Energy and Resources Institute (TERI) are beginning to draw upon these opportunities in some regions, but there are opportunities to expand this work across larger scales and regions to create nation-wide interlinked markets. *More details and actions are provided on page 52.*

Introduction

Blue Carbon in India

Blue carbon has been an emerging topic of interest since the term was coined in a United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) report in 2009 for its potential in climate change mitigation (Nellemann et al., 2009). Blue carbon refers to the carbon stored in coastal marine ecosystems, specifically mangroves, saltmarshes, and seagrasses. While the term blue carbon focuses on the climate change mitigation potential of these ecosystems, these ecosystems also have great potential as nature-based solutions providing benefits for climate, people and biodiversity (Austin et al., 2021). For example, they increase resilience of coastal communities by creating a buffer against flooding and sea level rise (described as a bioshield in India) and frequently enhance the health and productivity of fisheries in support of local livelihoods (Macreadie et al., 2021). However, it is important to note that nature-based solutions are not a substitute for a phase out of fossil fuels and should always aim to provide additional benefits to biodiversity and local communities (Seddon et al., 2021).

All three blue carbon ecosystems are present along India’s ~7,500-kilometre coastline, and India holds around 3% of the world’s mangrove forests. While there has been a significant output of research in the past several years on Indian blue carbon, there is still a great need for more research, particularly within saltmarshes and seagrasses which remain understudied. Further, blue carbon research is skewed towards certain geographic areas, with some regions being heavily researched and other relatively unexplored.

India is one of the world’s largest “recipient” countries for blue carbon – this means its country-specific social cost of carbon (CSCC)¹ is large, but its relative carbon sequestration potential is small, and therefore it benefits more from global carbon sequestration efforts than it contributes (Bertram et al., 2021). India’s status as a blue carbon wealth recipient however does not imply that India’s absolute carbon sequestration potential is necessarily small but instead highlights that the economic impact of climate change in India is very large, and therefore the country benefits greatly from the blue carbon contributions of other nations. India’s blue carbon potential is also yet to be completely recognised, as the total extent and status of its blue carbon ecosystems is not fully understood. Despite this, the economic and other impacts of climate change have been notable, as India continues to experience more extreme rainfall events, heat waves, extreme monsoon seasons, stronger cyclones, and corresponding impacts to agriculture, human health, and energy and water security (World Bank Group, 2013).

While the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change allows for the inclusion of blue carbon resources in national greenhouse gas (GHG) accounting if coastal wetlands are appropriately managed and restored as net sinks for atmospheric carbon dioxide, more research and synthesis is needed on blue carbon ecosystem extent, carbon stocks, and sequestration potential in order to consider blue carbon within India’s national GHG accounting. As a developing country with a net-zero target set for 2070 (rather than 2050, which is the case for most

¹ The specific social cost of carbon refers to the expected economic damages expected to be incurred by a country as a result of carbon dioxide emissions (Ricke et al., 2018).

developed nations), India's recent research efforts and policies have focused on climate adaptation and conservation. However, discussions with Indian blue carbon experts have demonstrated an aspiration to consider blue carbon ecosystems more comprehensively, in ways which account for the adaption *and* mitigation benefits of coastal ecosystem restoration. Further, exploring opportunities for climate change mitigation by protecting, restoring, and creating new blue carbon ecosystems starting now would allow India to proactively reduce its emissions and bring itself closer to its net-zero target, because blue carbon ecosystems accrue carbon in their sediment and biomass over long periods of time, and generally become greater carbon sinks as they age. This will also help India meet its interim Paris Agreement targets, namely of reducing emissions intensity of its GDP by 45 percent of 2005 levels by 2030, and to create an additional carbon sink of 2.5 to 3 billion tonnes of CO₂ equivalent through additional forest and tree cover by 2030 (Government of India, 2022).

India-UK Collaboration

In 2024, the UK became the first nation to map and estimate the carbon stored in its seabed sediments and vegetated habitats (The Wildlife Trusts, 2024). The UK is also home to the United Nations Global Ocean Decade Programme for Blue Carbon (led by the University of St Andrews) (GO BC, n.d.). This makes the UK well-placed to support blue carbon research efforts in other regions. These collaborations are already blossoming between the UK and India - in January 2024, experts and researchers from the UK and India held a blue carbon workshop at Ahmedabad University in Gujarat to discuss blue carbon initiatives in India and the UK, and to enhance global collaboration within the science-policy-societal interface. The workshop, supported by the Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs (DEFRA), focused on case studies from both the UK and India to discuss technical and policy issues and was one of several significant launch pads for ongoing collaboration between the UK and India on blue carbon.

Why should the UK and India develop a collaborative programme on blue carbon at this time?

Currently, as part of the UK commitment to the sustainable management of coastal and marine resources, the UK blue Carbon Evidence Partnership has agreed a Blue Carbon Evidence Needs Statement (UKBCEP, 2023). One of the commitments made is to “*work together as a collaborative blue carbon community, across the UK and with international partners, to address our evidence needs and ultimately bring about positive change to our blue carbon habitats to deliver social, cultural, environmental and economic benefits on a local, national and global scale*” (UKBCEP, 2023, p.21). For example, the UK blue carbon community is actively engaged in developing standardised methodologies and these same issues have been identified as a priority for India; there is therefore an opportunity for both the UK and Indian blue carbon scientific communities to continue to work together to achieve these goals. The UK has recently developed an expertise in emerging nature markets, including codes to guide the valuation and development of voluntary carbon markets (e.g. saltmarsh code – UKCEH, 2024); India presents a great wealth of natural capital in which such nature markets could be developed with the support of robust blue carbon evidence.

The study presented here is a next step in furthering this important collaboration, and its development has involved discussions with experts in blue carbon science within research and government institutions in India during a visit in March 2025, to identify mutually agreed-upon gaps. For example, mangrove research continues to advance in India driven by local scientific expertise,

while the limited availability of research on saltmarshes and seagrass could be improved through collaboration with the UK, where both seagrasses and saltmarshes have been the focus of a growing amount of research and policy discussions.

Study Objectives

This study consists of a rigorous literature review and policy scan of blue carbon opportunities in India, assessing the existing published evidence and identifying evidence gaps. Grey literature, including unpublished reports, findings, and insights, have been included in the review which have been obtained through a network of Indian scientists who are actively engaged in blue carbon research and through contacts made at the DEFRA-supported workshop held at Ahmedabad University in early 2024. The report will inform policy ambitions for blue carbon in India based on scientific evidence. It will provide the policy context needed to identify emerging opportunities and recommend actions to support blue carbon ambitions in India.

These objectives will be achieved by answering the following three questions:

Research Question 1: *What is the current state of blue carbon research and policy within India?*

- Which thematic subtopics and blue carbon ecosystems receive the most attention?
- What is the spatial distribution of the blue carbon ecosystem studies, and which states or regions in India are studied the most?
- Which institutions (e.g., academic, research, governmental) produce this evidence?

Research Question 2: *Where are the significant gaps within the scientific and grey literature?*

- Which regions/topics within blue carbon research are underrepresented in the current literature?
- What are the gaps in data availability and quality for blue carbon ecosystems in India? Are there certain media lacking (e.g., review papers, policy scans, etc.)?
- Which blue carbon ecosystems require more attention and how should these be prioritized?
- How well are the socio-economic impacts of blue carbon ecosystems covered in the existing literature?

Research Question 3: *How can the identified gaps be filled to create a cohesive picture to inform policymaking?*

- What recommendations can be developed based on the research?
- How can the UK Government, academia, and other relevant actors contribute to filling these research gaps?
- How can interdisciplinary collaboration enhance the understanding and integration of blue carbon research findings into existing and emerging policy in India?

Figure 1: Restored mangroves in Pichavaram Mangrove Forest, Tamil Nadu (credit: Lauren South)

Background on blue carbon in India

Mangrove

Mangroves are trees and shrubs that thrive in intertidal zones, having adapted to grow in waterlogged and low-oxygen soil. Their roots are often fully submerged in saline water. Mangrove ecosystems are hotspots for biodiversity and provide breeding, nursing and feeding grounds for fish, crustaceans and many other aquatic species. Mangroves also act as a natural buffer zone against storm surges and erosion. Furthermore, they are the most carbon-rich ecosystems in the world (Donato et al., 2011). Research has shown that mangrove reforestation has a greater carbon storage potential per hectare than afforestation (Song et al., 2023).

India is home to 3% of the world's mangrove cover (4,991.68 km²), accounting for 0.15% of the country's geographical area. During the colonial period mangroves were classified as forests and as such were exploited for timber and other products resulting in large-scale deforestations (Selvam, 2021). It is estimated that around 40% of mangroves were lost in the 19th century, but since 1987 there has been a positive trend in their recovery (Sahu et al., 2015). Mangroves are still monitored by the Forest Survey of India and protected under the Forest Conservation Act, 1980 if designated as a reserved forest. Mangroves that are not classified as forests are recognised as coastal wetlands and protected under the Coastal Zone Regulation Notification, 2019.

Seagrass

Seagrasses are flowering marine plants that grow either intertidally or fully submerged in shallow saline water. Seagrass meadows are highly productive habitats that act as fish nursery grounds, improve water quality by filtering and cycling nutrients and pollutants, and reduce wave energy of storm surges. Seagrass ecosystems are also significant for climate change mitigation, contributing to around 10% of the annual carbon sequestration in the ocean (Fourqurean et al., 2012).

Figure 2: Seagrass bed in Palk Bay. Image from Omcar Foundation.

Seagrass beds in India are estimated to cover 517 km² and consist of 14 seagrass species (Geevarghese et al., 2018). There is limited data available on historical changes in seagrass cover. The main stressors of these ecosystems are human-related activities such as trawler fishing, recreational boat use and runoff from coastal aquaculture and agriculture. In India, seagrass meadows are explicitly protected under the Coastal Regulation Zone Notification 2019, with other legislation indirectly used for the protection and conservation of seagrass.

Saltmarsh

Saltmarshes are vegetated coastal wetlands regularly inundated by salt water. Like other blue carbon ecosystems, these marshes offer numerous ecosystem services for humans, wildlife, and the environment, including carbon sequestration and flood protection. However, saltmarshes worldwide have been significantly damaged or lost due to land reclamation for agriculture, aquaculture, and urban development.

The extent of saltmarsh cover in India is not well-defined, with estimates ranging from 290 km² (**Viswanathan et al., 2020**) to **1,611 km² (SAC, 2011; Akhand et al., 2023)**. Viswanathan and colleagues (2020) argue that earlier studies significantly overestimate the saltmarsh cover in India by including all halophytic grasslands found in coastal areas. There is limited information available regarding changes in saltmarsh coverage. Saltmarshes are categorised as Ecologically Sensitive Areas (ESA) and protected under the Coastal Regulation Zone (CRZ) Notification 2019.

Figure 3: Saltmarsh in Gujarat (credit: Sheena Peteranna).

PART 1 – Literature Review on Blue Carbon and State of Research in India

Literature review methods

A rigorous literature review was conducted to assess the state of blue carbon research and current knowledge in India. Web of Science and SCOPUS databases were both scanned, using the following keywords:

("blue carbon" OR "soil organic carbon" OR "organic carbon") AND ("mangrove" OR "salt marsh" OR "saltmarsh" OR "tidal marsh" OR "seagrass*") AND ("India*" OR "Bay of Bengal" OR "Arabian Sea" OR "West Bengal" OR "Odisha" OR "Andhra Pradesh" OR "Tamil Nadu" OR "Kerala" OR "Maharashtra" OR "Goa" OR "Karnataka" OR "Gujarat" OR "Andaman" OR "Nicobar" OR "Lakshadweep")*

The abstracts of each article were examined to determine their relevance to the topic, and were selected based on the following inclusion criteria:

1. The article focuses on science/policy evidence relevant to blue carbon in India;
2. The article highlights important or novel analytical methodologies for blue carbon assessment (habitat extent, habitat cover change, habitat carbon stocks, habitat greenhouse gas emissions, etc.); or,
3. The article contains important background information (e.g., habitat management, habitat ecosystem services, etc.) on blue carbon in India necessary for a thorough review.

Articles were eliminated from the review based on the following exclusion criteria:

1. If the article is focused exclusively on ecosystem services which are not directly relevant to blue carbon;
2. If the article focuses on a region other than India; or,
3. If the article is written in a language other than English and cannot be translated.

Additional articles were included following the initial literature scan, including newly published articles, and relevant articles found in the “grey” literature that did not appear in the original scan.

Figure 4: Flow chart depicting literature methods. The search terms for this review were developed in consultation with the FCDO. These terms resulted in a total outcome of 644 papers across 2 databases. Paper abstracts were screened based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, which resulted in 191 papers. Following a closer investigation, an additional 11 papers were screened out, for a final of 180 papers included in the review.

Policy scan methods

To assess the current state of blue carbon policy in India and identify future opportunities for integrating blue carbon potential into policies and legislation, we conducted a comprehensive policy scan. First, we identified all relevant international and national policies and programmes based on the IUCN international policy framework for blue carbon ecosystems. Second, we used the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) FAOLEX Database to search for all pertinent national and state-level legislation (including laws, acts, regulations) and policies that relate to blue carbon ecosystems. This process was supplemented and confirmed by additional policies, plans, and legislation found through a thorough literature review. The FAOLEX Database categorises legislation into 17 broad themes, with a separate category for various types of policies. For our policy scan, we included legislation classified under climate change, disaster risk management, environment, fisheries, forestry, land and soil management, as well as sea and wild species and ecosystems.

We explored policies and legislation that included any of the following keywords: “blue carbon”, “mangrove”, “seagrass”, “salt marsh”, “tidal marsh”, “wetlands”, “coast”, “marine”, “forest”, “climate change”, “adaptation”, “mitigation”, “biodiversity”, “ecosystem”, “environment”, and “carbon”. Consequently, the identified policies and legislation, at both the national and state levels, were examined to determine if they contained any references to blue carbon or blue carbon ecosystems and, if so, whether these references were for adaptation, mitigation, biodiversity or other ecosystem services.

We then assessed each policy (including policies and legislation that currently do not include any reference to blue carbon ecosystems and their benefits) for its potential to incorporate blue carbon for adaptation, mitigation or biodiversity using a traffic light system:

- **Green** - assigned if the policy is highly relevant for blue carbon (e.g. existing policy/legislation includes some blue carbon ecosystems but not all) and/or has been identified as a key entry point for blue carbon by international organisations.
- **Amber** - assigned if there is some relevance that requires further assessment or has indirect benefits.
- **Red** - assigned if blue carbon is not relevant to the policy or legislation (includes amendments, notifications and repeals).
- **Blue** – assigned if all blue carbon ecosystems are already included in the policy or legislation (this however does not consider the success of the policy or legislation in achieving the relevant targets and would require separate assessment)

Finally, in Part 3, we provide an opportunity roadmap for integrating blue carbon into policies and legislation classified as highly relevant (green).

Geographic distribution of ecosystems

Mangrove

Mangrove extent has been estimated in various studies, including 14500 ha measured in Bhitarkanika, Odisha (Banerjee & Paul, 2022); 6,651 ha in the Mahanadi region (Odisha) (Sahu et al., 2016); and 98,000 ha in the Gulf of Kutch (Gujarat) (Sigamani et al., 2023). Approximately 60% of India's mangroves can be found along the east coast of the country, while 14% are found along the west coast and the remaining population is found within the Andaman and Nicobar Islands (Akhand et al., 2023). The world's largest mangrove forest, the Sundarbans, are shared between India and Bangladesh, and are the focus of much research. However, less than half of India's mangroves have been sampled for blue carbon estimates, and studies have frequently been focused towards the buffer regions of mangrove forests due to difficulty in accessing more remote sites (Akhand et al., 2023; Chanda & Akhand, 2023).

Figure 5: Blue carbon ecosystem distribution across India based on global point datasets (**Seagrass**: UNEP-WCMC, Short FT (2021). Global distribution of seagrasses (version 7.1). Seventh update to the data layer used in Green and Short (2003). Cambridge (UK): UN Environment World Conservation Monitoring Centre. Data DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34892/x6r3-d211>; **saltmarsh**: Mcowen C, Weatherdon LV, Bochove J, Sullivan E, Blyth S, Zockler C, Stanwell-Smith D, Kingston N, Martin CS, Spalding M, Fletcher S (2017). A global map of saltmarshes (v6.1). Biodiversity Data Journal 5: e11764. Paper DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.5.e11764>; Data DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34892/07vk-ws51>; **mangrove**: Nick Murray. (2022). nick-murray/coastTrain: v1.0 for manuscript submission (zenodo release) (v1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7080756>; **state boundaries**: <https://hub.arcgis.com/datasets/esriindia1::india-state-boundary-2021-/about>; **basemap**: ESRI.)

Seagrass

Seagrass estimated extent in Lakshadweep is 1200 ha (Jagtap 1998; Nobi et al., 2011). Within the Gulf of Kachchh, the extent is estimated at 2432.21 ha. Smaller patches of seagrass have been spotted in Goa which extend about 1 ha, and in Kadalundi, spanning approximately 2 ha (Patro et al., 2017; Kaladharan & Asokan, 2012). Palk Bay, Chilika Lake, and the Gulf of Mannar each contain an estimated 17529 ha, 8000ha, and 5515 ha, respectively (Subramanian et al., 2011; Pati et al., 2014; Raja et al., 2012). 2943.3 ha have been measured in Andaman and Nicobar Islands (Nobi et al., 2013). A study by Geevarghese et al. (2018) used satellite images to estimate seagrass extent along six India sites: Palk Bay, Gulf of Mannar, Gulf of Kachchh, Chilika Lake, Andaman & Nicobar, and the lagoon of Lakshadweep, resulted in an estimated extent of 516.59 km². Seagrass has not been thoroughly mapped in India and therefore the total extent is expected to be much larger this value (Mathur et al., 2021).

Saltmarsh

Gujarat, Tamil Nadu, and West Bengal comprise 85% of India's known total saltmarsh habitat (Akhand et al., 2023). As with seagrass, there is no complete assessment of saltmarsh habitat in India and the actual extent is likely larger than estimated here. Saltmarsh habitats in India are found in Andhra Pradesh (4000 ha), Gujarat (144300 ha), Maharashtra (600 ha) Tamil Nadu (6100 ha) and Andaman and Nicobar Islands (6000 ha) totalling to 161100 ha (SAC, 2011). This total extent has been confirmed by Banerjee et al. (2017) but challenged by (Viswanathan et al., 2020) who believe that this estimate includes all halophytic grasslands that should not be considered as saltmarsh and therefore estimate the total saltmarsh extent in India to be closer to 29000 ha. As with seagrass, satellite images have been used to estimate saltmarsh distribution along India's coastal region, with validation via ground truthing. Based on this assessment, saltmarshes are estimated to cover 290km² (Viswanathan et al., 2020).

Blue Carbon Stocks

Average organic carbon stocks within India's blue carbon ecosystems are moderate but below average as compared with other countries globally, with an estimated total blue carbon stock of 67.35 Tg C across India's ~7500km coastline (Coastal Carbon Network, 2024; Akhand et al., 2023). This has been confirmed through regional studies, including in mangroves in the southern Gulf of Kachchh which were found to have relatively low concentrations of organic carbon and organic matter as compared with other mangrove sites globally (Das et al., 2019). Total organic carbon within the sediments of the Sundarbans is similarly low (Ray & Shahraki, 2016). Mangrove carbon stock has also been estimated by the Forest Survey of India using field and satellite observations for all 12 states with mangroves (Singh et al., 2023).

Organic carbon sources

The large diversity in geography and climate across India's coastal areas results in large varieties in organic carbon sources within blue carbon ecosystems, and this topic has received a notable amount of attention in the Indian blue carbon literature.

In southeastern India, algal sources are found to contribute a large portion of sedimentary organic carbon in mangroves, providing a potential explanation for low overall organic carbon concentrations as compared with other southeast Asian mangroves which are supplied by more terrestrial sources (Ray et al., 2021). Similarly, Nazneen & Raju (2017) found marine sources such as phytoplankton and macroalgae to be major sources of organic matter within Chilika lagoon seagrasses. Conversely, researchers studying sources of organic matter in Bhitarkanika mangrove forest in the northeast found a relative dominance of terrestrial source organic matter (Mukherjee et al., 2019). A similarly high terrestrial influence was found in the Pichavaram estuarine-mangrove ecosystem, demonstrating how organic carbon sources can exist in a gradient even within a single ecosystem (Sarma et al., 2012; Prasad & Ramanathan, 2009; Krishna et al., 2015). This huge variability in organic carbon sources highlights that sources are highly dependent on local factors.

Organic carbon sources within Indian blue carbon ecosystems vary across regions and across time and are highly dependant on local factors such as barriers to water flow, adjacent ecosystems, and more.

Beyond simply identifying whether ecosystems contain primarily allochthonous or autochthonous organic matter, some researchers have also explored the sources more specifically, often using stable isotope or biomarker techniques. Researchers have found a relationship between suspended organic matter and chlorophyll a which suggested some organic carbon could be produced in situ by phytoplankton (Ray et al., 2015). Nazneen and Raju (2017) found the same relationship in seagrass sediments in Chilika lagoon resulting from low C/N ratios in surface sediments and cores. A study in the Sundarbans found that a significant fraction of available organic carbon in sediment is converted to glomalin related soil protein by mycorrhizal fungi, which results in long-term storage within the sediment (Das et al., 2020). Hershey et al. (2021) found evidence that high concentrations of organic carbon could be associated with mangrove litter, a terrestrial source, within the semi-enclosed Mangalavanam Coastal Wetland in southwestern India. The same was found by Rani et al. (2021) in various semi-enclosed mangrove habitats in Cochin. Sanyal et al. (2020) measured dissolved organic carbon fluxes within estuaries in the Sundarbans in the northeast and found higher concentrations during the post-monsoon season which was also associated with high mangrove litterfall. In the Godavari estuary, variability in isotopic distribution across the estuary indicated multiple sources of organic matter.

Organic carbon sources can also vary over time. For example, sediment towards the bottom of cores in Vaitarna estuary were found to have higher levels of organic matter of terrestrial origin, as compared to at the top of the cores, indicating that the site was previously more hydrodynamically active and is now calmer (Volvoikar et al., 2014). These conditions are thought to be due to reduced rainfall, and the diversion of freshwater influx through the establishment of new dams. In a study in the Cochin River, a marine-dominated estuary, an increase in terrestrial origin carbon was deemed to have been modified by adjacent deforestation (Passos et al., 2022).

Soil Organic Carbon Stocks

The soil organic carbon stock in mangroves was assessed at 55 sites across 17 studies (see Table 1A). The carbon stock ranged from 431.83 MgC/ha in Chediyatapu, Andaman and Nicobar Islands, to 3.52 MgC/ha in Habalikhati, Odisha (Banerjee et al., 2021). In contrast, carbon stock for seagrass was estimated in five studies from 14 sites. While mangroves had multiple replicates for carbon stock assessments, seagrass ecosystems often had their carbon stock measured as an average over larger areas. The seagrass carbon stock varied from 184.24 MgC/ha in the Andaman and Nicobar Islands to 0.998 MgC/ha in Pulicat Lake (Stankovic et al., 2021; Kaladharan et al., 2020). Only two studies evaluated soil organic carbon stock in saltmarshes across 11 sites. Both the lowest and highest saltmarsh carbon stock values were recorded at the same site; the lowest was found in dry saltmarsh soil, while the highest was in wet saltmarsh soil in Tuticorin (Kaviarasan et al., 2019).

Soil organic carbon stocks ranged from **431.83 MgC/ha** (mangrove in Andaman and Nicobar Islands) to **0.998 MgC/ha** (seagrass in Odisha). This order of magnitude difference is likely due to significant differences in core depth and stock calculation methods.

Figure 6: Soil organic carbon stock in mangroves, seagrass, and saltmarshes in India. All stocks are reported as MgC/ha (see Table 1A). Stocks are reported in the published literature using different core depths and do not therefore represent a standard (1m) soil organic carbon stock (basemap: ESRI).

The difference of two orders of magnitude in stock values for both mangroves and seagrasses are likely due to differences in stock calculations, and differences in soil core depths. Core depths range between 0-5 cm and 189 cm and are reported in Table 1A. IPCC guidance indicates a standard reporting depth of 1 m should be used for soil carbon stock assessments for accurate measurements of associated greenhouse gas inventories (Kennedy et al., 2013). These values, as well as vegetation and total ecosystem organic carbon stocks, are shown side by side in Figure 1A.

Vegetation Organic Carbon Stocks

Organic carbon stocks in vegetation were less common within the literature than those for soil organic carbon. This is likely because the search terms of this review specified “soil organic carbon” but not “vegetation organic carbon”. As such, there were four papers which published vegetation stocks for mangroves across 17 sites, one paper on vegetation stocks in seagrass across 4 sites, and no measurements of saltmarsh vegetation stocks.

Figure 7: Vegetation organic carbon stock in mangrove and seagrass (no saltmarsh data) in India (basemap: ESRI).

Total Ecosystem Organic Carbon Stocks

Records of total ecosystem carbon were less common than soil carbon measurements, but more common than vegetation carbon measurements. Total ecosystem carbon was measured at 24 mangrove sites, with the largest value recorded in Kochi, Kerala (335.33 MgC/ha) and the smallest value recorded at Bhitarkhanasi, Odisha (51.35 MgC/ha) (Rani et al., 2023; Banerjee et al., 2021). Only two measurements of ecosystem organic carbon stock from seagrasses were reported in the literature, both taken within the Andaman and Nicobar Islands, ranging from 988 MgC (across 144 ha) to 184.24 MgC/ha (Mishra et al., 2023; Stankovic et al., 2021). There were also two measurements recorded for saltmarshes: 49.58 MgC/ha at Bhitarkanika, Odisha, and 49.73 MgC/ha at Mahanadi, Odisha (Banerjee et al., 2022a).

Figure 8: Total ecosystem organic carbon stock in mangroves, seagrass, and saltmarshes in India (basemap: ESRI).

Distribution of Research by State

Figure 9 shows the distribution of published research by Indian state based on the findings of 149 papers in this review. The remaining 31 papers were either literature reviews and/or did not have specific regional focuses. Every coastal state has at least one blue carbon study. Three states show very high study concentrations: West Bengal (48 studies), Odisha (32 studies), and Tamil Nadu (23 studies). Kerala (13 studies), Goa (11 studies), Andaman and Nicobar (7 studies), and Maharashtra (7 studies) show an intermediate number of studies. The lowest number of studies come from Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh (3 studies each), Karnataka, and Lakshadweep (1 study each). Importantly,

these counts are likely not representative of blue carbon ecosystem density within India. For example, Gujarat has a relatively low concentration of publications, despite being one of the three Indian states with the highest identified concentrations of saltmarsh, and ~24% of India’s mangrove cover (Akhand et al., 2021; Mathur et al., 2021). Similarly, there is evidence from global datasets (Figure 1) that Karnataka has potentially large concentrations of seagrasses, however this is not reflected in the study concentrations.

Figure 9: Number of studies published with research sites in each Indian state (state boundaries: <https://hub.arcgis.com/datasets/esriindia1::india-state-boundary-2021-/about>, basemap: ESRI)

Figure 10 shows the number of blue carbon studies in this review plotted against the blue carbon ecosystem (mangrove, seagrass, and saltmarsh) extent in each state, based on the findings of this review and the India State of Forest Report 2021 (State of Forest Report (ISFR) 2021, 2022). Most states show an evenly representative number of studies compared with total ecosystem extent, apart from Gujarat, which is considered to have the largest extent of blue carbon in the country but has been the subject of comparatively few papers.

Figure 10: Blue carbon ecosystem (mangrove, seagrass, and saltmarsh) extent (x axis) based on this review and the [India State of Forest Report 2021](#) compared with number of blue carbon studies (y axis) in this review. Ecosystem extent is likely underestimated in most states as seagrass and saltmarsh extents have been understudied.

Factors influencing carbon storage

The existing blue carbon research in India has explored many of the factors which influence carbon storage. Consistent with the data on carbon stocks above, most of the research is focused on mangrove ecosystems and estuaries.

Water parameters

Freshwater supply

Changes in freshwater supply to mangrove ecosystems can have varying impacts on carbon storage. For example, in measurements from an estuary which received a good supply of uninterrupted freshwater input (the Dharma estuary), organic carbon concentrations were higher than compared to an estuary which had a reduced freshwater influx. However, as

Tidal amplitudes can play a significant role in blue carbon ecosystem distribution, while salinity can control species composition and CO₂ and CH₄ emissions from blue carbon ecosystems. Lower salinity has been associated with higher CH₄ emissions, while higher salinity has been associated with a lower blue carbon pool.

freshwater input can have either a negative or positive feedback on air-water CO₂ flux, the study found no significant difference between the mean sedimentary organic carbon concentrations of the two estuaries (Akhand et al., 2021).

Tides

Intertidal mangrove sediments within the Sundarbans are exposed to significant remineralisation processes and organic matter transformation, which result in lower organic carbon concentrations as compared with other mangrove sites globally (from a study of several estuaries along the Ganges, including the Hooghly estuary) (Ray et al., 2015). Differences in tidal amplitudes can also impact the presence of blue carbon ecosystems, particularly saltmarshes. For example, the Gujarat province contains a large fraction of India's total saltmarshes in part due to high tidal amplitudes, meaning a larger area can be flooded at high tide resulting a wider marsh extent (Viswanathan et al., 2020). Large tides such as those present in the Sundarbans can also have a strong influence on carbon outputs from the ecosystem, flushing dissolved carbon into mangrove creeks and subsequently into the Bay of Bengal (Tait et al., 2024).

Salinity

Salinity can also influence carbon storage indirectly as it often controls species composition, biodiversity, and, subsequently, biomass. There is a strong relationship between organic carbon and salinity within mangrove ecosystems in particular (Ray et al., 2015). A saltmarsh study from the Bhitarkanika wildlife sanctuary found higher biomass at stations with moderate to low salinity, demonstrating that certain species may require low salinity in their early development stage (Banerjee et al., 2022). Changes in precipitation regimes under climate change could result in regional increases in salinity, which could in turn result in shifts in species composition within mangrove forests (Wylie et al., 2016; Rasquinha & Mishra, 2021; Chanda & Akhand, 2023). Salinity can also influence the carbon balance of an ecosystem: in a study of mangrove sediments in Goa, Nazareth & Gonsalves (2022) found that a decrease in salinity could be linked to an increase in methane, and this strong relationship has been reinforced elsewhere, as has the relationship between increased soil salinity and a reduced blue carbon pool (Gnanamoorthy et al., 2022; Banerjee et al., 2022b; Das & Mandal, 2022; Ray et al., 2015; Das et al., 2023; Chowdhury et al., 2023).

Salinity shifts can also impact seagrass distribution and seagrass meadow composition, as some seagrass species are sensitive to fluctuations in salinity (Acharyya et al., 2023). This was demonstrated in Chilika lagoon, Odisha, where changes in salinity conditions resulted in a shift in species composition of seagrass (Ramesh et al., 2019).

Soil parameters

Grain size

There has been a considerable amount of research within Indian blue carbon ecosystems on grain size and its relationship with organic carbon concentration. Trends in mangrove grain

Finer grain size (e.g., muddy and silty sediment) is associated with higher organic carbon, and mangroves and seagrass sediments in Indian sites have been found to contain finer sediments than surrounding areas.

size and organic carbon concentration are abundant within the literature reviewed. In a study by Ratheesh Kumar et al. (2022) exploring lipid biomarkers within mangrove environments in Cochin, the researchers found significantly higher concentrations of biomarkers in the fine sediment-dominated systems, due to greater preservation of organic matter under low oxygen conditions (Kumar et al., 2022). This is exemplified in the Vellar-Coleroon estuary, where total organic carbon content was higher in planted mangrove sediments as compared with sandy soils (Saravanakumar et al., 2016; Saravanakumar et al., 2018).

Mangrove forests tend to have finer-grained sediments as compared to estuaries and mudflats, owing to the low hydrodynamic energy conditions that mangroves experience by nature of their complex aerial roots systems (Ratheesh Kumar et al., 2022; Nayak et al., 2018; Bhangle et al., 2021). A study by Bhangle et al. (2021) based in the Mandovi estuary, Goa, found that owing to the larger grain size in mudflats, more water infiltration is able to occur which can wash away toxins, while mangrove sediments in contrast tended to have higher metal concentrations. Organic carbon concentration is often associated with grain size, and this study correspondingly found higher concentrations of organic carbon in muddy mangrove sediment as compared with adjacent bare sediment. The same trend is visible in seagrass sediments within Chilika lagoon, where organic carbon concentrations were lower in the outer channel of the lagoon which consisted of coarser-grained sediments (Nazneen & Raju, 2017). A study of organic matter sources within mangroves and saltmarshes in Pichavaram wetlands found that organic carbon in mangrove sediments tended to be higher as compared with saltmarshes, likely due to the ability of mangrove, by nature of their roots, to better accumulate and retain finer particles that are associated with organic carbon (Naidu et al., 2022).

Grain size can vary depending on site location within estuaries, resulting in a gradient of organic matter concentrations. Krishna et al. (2015) found that higher levels of clay and silt content often found within the sediments of the lower portion of an estuary generated favourable conditions for higher concentrations of organic matter, as compared with the upper estuary. Higher turbidity in the lower estuary from increased mixing also limited light availability for phytoplankton production, which resulted in higher organic matter preservation in the lower estuary (Krishna et al., 2015). However, grain size distribution is not consistent across estuaries, as Nayak (2020) and Singh et al. (2013) both found finer sediment upstream as compared to downstream within a mudflat in the Zuari estuary. Thus, these processes are heavily dependent on changing hydrodynamic conditions.

Ecosystem connectivity and deposition over time

Ecosystem connectivity

Blue carbon ecosystems rarely exist in isolation of the ecosystems surrounding them. These connected ecosystems influence each other's productivity, and subsequently they influence each other's carbon storage capacity (Alikunhi & Kathiresan, 2012). Pillai Ranith et al. (2024) found that the presence of coral reefs adjacent to seagrasses in Palk Bay enhanced the blue carbon potential of the seagrasses by comparing the carbon stocks in seagrass meadows adjacent to coral reefs and those without coral reefs.

Indian blue carbon ecosystems are more productive when connected to adjacent ecosystems. Of the blue carbon ecosystems in India, evidence points towards mangroves having the greatest sediment accumulation rates, indicating a likelihood that mangroves sequester organic carbon at higher rates than seagrasses and saltmarshes.

Connections with inland ecosystems can also influence blue carbon systems. A study conducted along a transect of different ecosystems on Andaman Island found increasing concentrations of soil organic carbon from a deciduous forest on a hilltop towards a mangrove forest along the coast (Velmurugan et al., 2022).

In a study in the Gautami-Godavari estuary of Goa, Krishna et al. (2015) investigated the major sources of organic matter to identify what was controlling the distribution and preservation of organic matter in the sediments of this estuary. The researchers found that there were higher concentrations of soil organic carbon in the lower estuary, despite higher levels of primary production in the upper estuary, which indicated that favourable conditions and preservation processes are more important in controlling sediment organic matter content as compared with primary production (Krishna et al., 2015).

Sedimentation rates

Sedimentation rates directly impact blue carbon stocks as they control the level of organic matter accumulating within an environment. Sediment accumulation rates have been demonstrated to be higher in mangrove ecosystems (4.5 mm/yr) as compared with saltmarshes (accumulation rate of closer to 1.6 mm/yr) (Ranjan et al., 2010; Naidu et al., 2022), which indicates a likelihood that mangroves will be able to sequester more organic carbon than saltmarshes. However, research by Mishra and Farooq (2022) on saltmarshes across India found that sedimentation rates can be species-dependent, with some species' deeper root systems (e.g., *P. Coarctata*) can result in higher sedimentation rates. This could be the case for mangroves as well. Volvoikar et al. (2014) found that in the Vaitarna estuary, coarser sediment was favoured in the estuary under previous conditions, but recent changes have resulted in calmer conditions that have favoured the deposition of finer particles.

Variability in land-use adjacent to blue carbon ecosystems can regulate organic matter sources across the gradient of a single ecosystem. For example, regional differences in land use across the

Sundarbans result in a higher input of terrestrial carbon upstream and a higher marine influence downstream (Prasad et al., 2017)

Seagrasses have a strong influence on community composition and play a critical role in organic matter cycling and deposition in the other coastal ecosystems of Chilika Lagoon (Mohapatra et al., 2022). Their role in accelerating sedimentation stems from the tendency of seagrasses to trap and subsequently deposit previously suspended sediments, resulting in high sedimentary organic carbon stocks.

Heavy metal concentrations, biofouling

Heavy metals

Heavy metal contamination has received a significant amount of research within Indian mangroves. Heavy metals have been detected across many mangrove sites, including the Vellar-Coleroon estuary, Pichavaram mangroves (Sundaramanickam et al., 2016), and others. Vellar-Coleroon and Pichavaram were found to have high concentrations

Higher heavy metal contamination has been frequently identified at mangrove sites and is associated with human activity. Higher concentrations of heavy metals are associated with a reduction in the health of mangrove ecosystems.

of iron and manganese ($11,804 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ and $845.2 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, respectively) (Sundaramanickam et al., 2016). Organic carbon in sediment (along with grain size and other parameters) plays a role in the distribution and accumulation of certain heavy metals, as rich organic matter acts as a suitable binding agent (Fernandes & Nayak, 2009; Fernandes et al., 2014; Sundaramanickam et al., 2016; Nayak, 2020). Fernandes et al. (2014) found that higher organic carbon concentrations coincided with higher metal concentrations (such as manganese) from anthropogenic sources. Sundaramanickam et al. (2016) found that the accumulation of heavy metals can result from differences in organic matter within different ecosystems. In a study by Volvoikar et al. (2014), sand, silt, and clay, all common in mangrove settings, were all found to be strongly associated with metals.

Mangroves can be significantly impacted by elevated heavy metal concentrations. In a study conducted in Serthalaikkadu Creek, Muthupet, researchers found a clear link between anthropogenic activities to trace metal concentrations which, along with deforestation, and thought to be the cause of degradation to the creek (Sundararajan & Natesan, 2011). Proximity to mining areas has also been found to influence heavy metal proximity within intertidal estuaries in Goa (Singh et al., 2013; Nayak et al., 2018).

Biofouling

Only one example of biofouling was found through the scope of this literature review. A study in the mangroves of Vasishtthi estuary in Maharashtra found that oysters damage to mangrove root systems appears to have damaged the roots' capacity to hold sediment, leading to a lower ability to retain organic matter and resulting in erosion (Panchang, 2015) (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Oyster infestation on mangrove aerial roots and mudflats and associated erosion. Image taken from Panchang, 2015.

Biodiversity

While biodiversity was not a direct focus of this review, it is evident from the existing research that biodiversity has a clear impact on blue carbon stock. For example, Punniyamoorthy et al. (2021) studied the structure of meiofauna in different types of mangrove ecosystems to explore their role in blue carbon cycling and found higher abundances of meiofaunal in mangrove sites as compared with a non-mangrove site. This indicates the need for more research on whether there is a symbiotic relationship between mangroves and meiofauna.

Biodiversity has a strong influence on blue carbon stock because in general healthy ecosystems are able to store more organic carbon.

A study on phytoplankton primary productivity in ecotones within the Gulf of Mannar Biosphere reserve demonstrated the importance of organic matter generated within mangrove ecosystems to increasing the primary productivity within adjacent ecosystems (Alikunhi & Kathiresan, 2012). Notably, mangrove ecosystems demonstrated a better ability to do this as compared with coral reefs (Alikunhi & Kathiresan, 2012).

In addition to evidence that healthy mangroves are capable of storing larger amounts of organic carbon as compared with degraded mangroves, higher amounts of organic carbon in sediments supports the natural regeneration of some mangrove species, as shown by a study in the southern Gulf of Kachchh (Das et al., 2019).

Seasonal Variation

Across the seasons, there can be significant variations in salinity, light intensity, turbidity, and dissolved organic nutrients (including organic carbon) within estuaries and adjacent mangrove forests (Alikunhi & Kathiresan, 2012; Resmi et al., 2016). This is often driven by the presence of allochthonous organic matter, which can inject organic carbon into an ecosystem from upstream freshwater sources that are seasonally variable (Seleyi et al., 2024).

Seasonal variation plays a significant role in regulating many of the other parameters listed so far, including salinity, deposition and accumulation, freshwater supply, nutrient concentrations, and more.

Arumugam et al. (2013) found that temporal and spatial variations in seagrass meadows in the Gulf of Mannar often corresponded with seasonal variations, particularly with the monsoon season, and that particulate organic carbon was one of the physicochemical parameters that strongly influenced this variation in seagrass meadows (Arumugam et al., 2013).

A study by Chaudhary et al. (2018) explored the seasonal biomass of saltmarshes in Gujarat and found that highest aboveground biomass and aboveground carbon pool values were found in March (2.1 t ha^{-1}). The researchers also found a positive correlation between belowground biomass and organic carbon (Chaudhary et al., 2018).

Within mangrove systems, Brown and Hale (2022) studied depositional features in the Sundarbans and found that although sediment and freshwater supply vary seasonally, deposition rates remained constant.

Emissions and carbon balance

Depending on the factors explored above, blue carbon ecosystems can behave either as carbon sinks or carbon sources, via emission of carbon dioxide (CO_2) and/or methane (CH_4) (Nazareth & Gonsalves, 2022). For example, despite emitting CH_4 , saltmarshes are still found to be overall good carbon sinks (Banerjee et al., 2022a). Similarly, Indian seagrass meadows are considered net sinks despite their ability to act as minor sources of CO_2 due to anthropogenic influence (Ganguly et al., 2018; Banerjee et al., 2018). Generally, mangrove ecosystems are considered carbon sinks when an entire ecosystem is considered as a whole, whereas if the different components of an ecosystem are measured separately, then the surrounding water and soils of the ecosystem can act as CO_2 sources (Akhand et al., 2024).

Estuaries can be sinks or sources of CO_2 to the atmosphere, depending heavily on the processing of organic matter within individual estuaries. Estuaries can be sources of CO_2 emissions if the biogeochemical activity within the estuaries makes them heterotrophic and subsequently net

sources of CO₂ to the atmosphere (Akhand et al., 2021; Ray et al., 2015). The heterotrophy or autotrophy of an estuarine system can follow distinct seasonal patterns (Seleyi et al., 2024; Krishna et al., 2015). For example, researchers found higher CH₄ and N₂O emissions within Bhitarkanika mangroves during the winter season as compared with the summer and monsoon seasons (Chauhan et al., 2015). In investigating the nature of CH₄ production in the Sundarbans, researchers found that the region acted as a CH₄ source during the monsoon season, but as a sink during both the pre and post monsoon seasons (Dutta et al., 2013). However, these variations have generally been understudied within India's monsoonal estuaries.

A study comparing the Hooghly estuary with estuaries in the Sundarbans found that the heavily anthropogenically influenced Hooghly estuary acted as a much larger source of CO₂ emissions as compared with the Sundarbans estuaries, demonstrating that carbon cycling is quite variable across estuaries, and that CO₂ emissions are higher in anthropogenically influenced estuaries (Kumar Dutta et al., 2019). In a review of carbon and nutrient fluxes in the coastal zone, Alongi et al. (2013) predict that a reduction in wetlands due to coastal zone development and other human activities combined with a reduction in freshwater input could indicate a shift towards more consistently heterotrophic environments, and increasingly sources of CO₂ to the atmosphere.

Table 1: CH₄ and CO₂ emissions from blue carbon ecosystems in India (as reported).

Blue carbon ecosystem	What is being measured (CO ₂ /CH ₄)	Location	Value (mean ± SD)	Units	Reference
Mangrove	Mean potential CO ₂ emission from degradation of ABG between 1975 and 2013	Sundarbans	1567.98 ± 551.69	Gg	(Akhand et al., 2017)
Mangrove	CH ₄ emissions	Mandovi	1268.68 ± 176	nM/cm ² /ha	(Nazareth & Gonsalves, 2022)
Mangrove	Daily mean CH ₄ flux (wet season)	Pichavaram	12-26	nmol/m ² /sec	(Gnanamoorthy et al., 2022)
Mangrove	Daily mean CH ₄ flux (dry season)	Pichavaram	6-20	nmol/m ² /sec	
Mangrove	CH ₄ flux	Sundarbans	0.004–0.63	mgC/m ² /hr	(Arai et al., 2016)
Mangrove	CH ₄ flux	Sundarbans	159	µg/ m ² /hr	(Padhy et al., 2023)
Mangrove	CH ₄ flux in converted ecosystem	Sundarbans	2665	µg/ m ² /hr	
Mangrove	CH ₄ flux	Sundarbans	408 +/- 110	nmol/m ² /hr	(Dutta et al., 2013)
Seagrass	CH ₄ flux	Chilika	0.05 – 0.12	mM/m ² /day	(Banerjee et al., 2018)
Seagrass	CO ₂ flux	Chilika	9.8 – 146.6	mM/m ² /day	

Threats to Blue Carbon ecosystems

Human uses

Human uses, including dumping, fishing, conversion to aquaculture, tourism, and subsistence uses, are all capable of influencing the carbon storage capacity of blue carbon ecosystems. In a study looking at two different estuaries (Malta and Hooghly estuary), it was found that human influence resulted in more labile

Human activities, from hydrological modifications to mining operations, most often result in degradation to blue carbon ecosystems which subsequently results in lower blue carbon stores.

organic matter within the Hooghly estuary (Fischer et al., 2016). As labile organic matter is more prone to disturbance, this influence is likely to have a negative impact on the estuary's carbon stock. Similarly, in a study of organic matter sources in a mangrove forest in Cochin, researchers found that increased urbanisation and subsequent changes in soil nutrient and microbe composition shifted the lagoon from oligotrophic to hypertrophy, transforming the organic matter from its more labile form into more refractory organic matter (Cheriyian et al., 2022).

A study of benthic foraminifera assemblages in the Sundarbans found calcareous organisms consistent with higher salinity than would be expected based on site salinity, suggesting increased salinity intrusion due to relative sea level rise and anthropogenic factors such as the building of dams (Sen et al., 2016). Changes in salinity are likely to impact species composition and biodiversity, including of sedimentary biota, which could correspondingly have impacts on organic carbon dynamics. A study in the Andaman and Nicobar Islands found that land use had a notable impact on soil properties such as microbial properties and enzymes, which influence mineralisation and carbon storage (Velmurugan et al., 2022). These properties can increase carbon storage but also sometimes have the opposite effect, possibly due to feedbacks at different trophic levels.

Conversion to agriculture can result in changes to the biological makeup of mangrove ecosystems such as algae abundance, which can also have impacts on mangrove carbon storage and on adjacent ecosystems. Empirically, mangrove ecosystems have been shown to have higher soil organic carbon concentrations compared with agricultural soils, indicating that conversion has a quantitatively negative impact on soil carbon stores (Velmurugan et al., 2022). In a study in the Sundarbans mangroves, conversion of mangroves to rice-based cropping systems corresponded with a shift in dominant algae species, because of changes in soil nutrients, salinity, and alkalinity. While some newly abundant algae species have shown promise for increasing mangrove carbon sequestration potential, more studies are needed to determine the net effect of these composition shifts (Nayak et al., 2024).

A study on hydrodynamic interactions in the Zuari river estuary, Goa, found that due to anthropogenic land cover and hydrological modifications, the estuary exports far less particulate organic carbon ($20 \times 10^3 \text{ kg yr}^{-1}$) as compared with other river estuary systems in the tropics. These types of river estuary systems generally have high runoff and deliver a notable fraction of sediment

and carbon into the ocean globally, which contributes to the global carbon cycle. When this process is disrupted, this particulate organic carbon is trapped in estuarine environments, affecting the estuarine biogeochemistry (Pradhan et al., 2020).

Other disturbances

In addition to disturbances which are the direct result of human activity, natural and indirect forms of disturbance can influence blue carbon ecosystems in India. Examples of this in the current literature include sea level rise, cyclones, and excessive herbivory.

Cyclones can have significant impacts on mangrove ecosystems, as they result in hydrological and structural changes to ecosystems. The most significant impacts noted for seagrass meadows are herbivory by green turtles and greater light attenuation from sea level rise.

The impact of sea level rise has not been explored in great detail so far within the context of Indian blue carbon; therefore, the magnitude of these changes cannot be directly quantified. For example, sea level rise and increased tidal variability are anticipated to reduce light availability at the depth of current seagrass meadows in Palk Bay, which could affect the photosynthetic capacity of seagrass (Purvaja et al., 2020). Contrastingly, an increase in ambient temperature and a resulting increase in dissolved CO₂ could increase the photosynthetic performance of seagrass (Purvaja et al., 2020). In one of the few saltmarsh related studies captured in this review, researchers found low concentrations of organic matter in the lower portion of the marsh, which they hypothesize is due to greater saltwater intrusion associated with sea level rise (Saha et al., 2022).

Chaudhuri et al. (2009) found that a tsunami in December 2004 had impacts on soil physicochemical and microbial properties. The changes in topography, salinity, and water inflow led to soil degradation and a reduction in microbial activity and biomass at disturbed sites as compared with undisturbed sites (Chaudhuri et al., 2009). Rasquinha and Mishra (2021) explored the theory that cyclones increase the productivity of mangroves as a result of nutrient fertilisation through a review of the existing literature and found increasing trends in gross primary productivity following cyclones as a result of nutrient enrichment.

Gangal et al. (2021) explored the impact of foraging green turtles on seagrasses in the Lakshadweep archipelago, finding that overgrazing of the turtles resulted in reduced seagrass extent and stored organic carbon in the sediment. The researchers found that all the studied meadows had experienced some level of depletion, which had the potential to result in functional extinction of seagrasses (Gangal et al., 2021).

Challenges for restoration and management of blue carbon ecosystems

There have been a variety of mangrove and other blue carbon ecosystem restoration projects in India in recent years, executed with varying degrees of success. Challenges that hinder the success of

restoration projects include illegal deforestation, livestock grazing, and aquaculture within new plantations, recognising the need for community involvement to support mangrove monitoring and design projects compatible with community wellbeing and local economies (Wylie et al., 2016). Similarly, a study in the Sundarbans by Chowdhury et al. (2024) showed that community participation is vital in multispecies mangrove restoration success. Dhyani et al. (2023) highlight the need for including traditional and indigenous knowledge and acknowledging the human-natural system interactions for successful restoration projects. A model of optimal community-led mangrove restoration in the Sundarbans suggested that in the absence of outside support through wages or reimbursement of costs, restoration efforts can take a long time, leaving communities more vulnerable to the risks of cyclones (Ranjan, 2019). However, long-term restoration projects can derive better outcomes for global carbon mitigation efforts (Ranjan, 2019).

Not all restoration efforts have been completely successful. For example, mangrove restoration programmes have been reported to cause the loss of saltmarsh *Porterasia coarctata* habitats because mangrove saplings are planted within the *P. coarctata* habitats and fully grown mangroves create anoxic sediment hindering the growth of saltmarsh plants (Mishra and Farooq, 2022). One of the explanations for unsuccessful mangrove projects results from the consideration of mangrove ecosystems as public goods, resulting in a market failure (Ghosh, 2019).

Scan of Blue Carbon Policy

We reviewed 102 international, international and state level policies and legislation (Figure 12). Below is a summary of how India has included blue carbon ecosystems in international and national policies, and national and state level legislation (see Annex A Table 4A for a detailed description of each policy and legislation of which blue ecosystems and in what capacity (adaptation, mitigation, biodiversity or other ecosystem services) they are included.

The term 'blue carbon' is not mentioned in any Indian policy or legislation. Mangroves are the most recognised blue carbon ecosystem in policies and legislation and are mainly highlighted for their adaptation benefits and other ecosystem services.

■ Policies under international frameworks (5) ■ National policies (11) ■ National legislation (20) ■ State level policies and legislation (66)

Figure 12: Assessment of blue carbon ecosystem inclusion in policies and legislation. Overall, we identified 5 policies under international frameworks, 11 national policies, 20 national legislation and 66 state-level policies and legislation and assessed their current inclusion of blue carbon ecosystems – mangroves, saltmarsh and seagrass. A mention of each blue carbon ecosystem was counted separately in each document, but more than one ecosystem could be mentioned, therefore the total number of documents does not equal the sum of mentions of each ecosystem.

Influence of international policy frameworks

The key international policy frameworks to ensure effective conservation and restoration of blue carbon ecosystems and their inclusion in national policies are the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands of International Importance (Ramsar Convention) and the 2030 Agenda and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

International policy processes aim to strengthen commitment to the conservation and restoration of coastal ecosystems by recognising blue carbon ecosystems in climate action plans and establishing ambitious targets and commitments. In the required international policy frameworks, India has recognised blue carbon ecosystem adaptation, mitigation and biodiversity benefits (Figure 13).

Figure 13: The capacity to what blue carbon ecosystems is included – adaptation, mitigation, biodiversity or other ecosystem services (e.g. nursery for fisheries). No national legislation or state-level legislation and state policy referred to only to mitigation potential of blue carbon ecosystems. Details for each included policy or legislation are available in Table A3.

The key entry points under the UNFCCC framework are the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and National Adaptation Plans (NAPs). NDCs are submitted every five years to the UNFCCC secretariat. The most recent NDCs were submitted in February 2025 for the time frame up to 2035. Mangroves were mentioned in India's Intended Nationally Determined Contribution published in 2015 (MoEFCC, 2015) as measure for protecting coastal livelihoods, but did not feature in the newest

version (MoEFCC, 2022a). India's National Action Plan for Climate Change (NAPCC) was published in 2008 and consists of eight missions. While it does not directly include any of the blue carbon ecosystems, the National Coastal Mission Scheme was launched in 2014 under the NAPCC. It aims to address the impact of climate change on coastal and marine ecosystems, infrastructure and communities in coastal areas through a combination of adaptation and mitigation measures. However, it is not yet fully implemented. The entry points for measuring, reporting and accounting for blue carbon and blue carbon ecosystems under the UNFCCC include Global Stocktake, National GHG inventories and Biennial Transparency reports. Blue carbon is not explicitly included in India's GHG inventory, but under mitigation actions for the forestry sector in the Fourth Biennial Update Report (BUR-4) (MoEFCC, 2024), the Mangrove Initiative for Shoreline Habitats and Tangible Income (MISHTI) has been recognised for its mitigation potential. However, detailed GHG emissions by sources and removals by sinks are not estimated for wetlands.

The National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP) aligning with the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), is an essential framework that helps countries incorporate biodiversity conservation into their development objectives. The updated NBSAP is now in line with the goals and targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, adopted in 2022. India's updated NBSAP (2024-2030) recognises all established blue carbon ecosystems for biodiversity. Inadequate protection of coastal and marine ecosystems has been acknowledged as a gap along with increased attention and investments of wetlands and coastal ecosystems. Coastal habitats and wetlands are explicitly included in National Biodiversity Targets and Action Points 1, 2, 3, 8, 10, 20. While the previous NBSAP 2018 mentioned carbon stocks of forests, including mangroves, this information is not included in the updated NBSAP.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were adopted in 2015 to ensure a collective global effort toward meeting urgent environmental, social and economic needs. There are 17 SDGs with SDG14 Life Below Water being the most relevant to blue carbon. In India, the overall responsibility of SDGs implementation and aligning government schemes and programmes to SDGs lies with the National Institution for Transforming India (NITI Aayog). There are seven targets that SDG 14 aims to achieve of which two are directly related to blue carbon ecosystems: (14.2) By 2020, sustainably manage and protect marine and coastal ecosystems to avoid significant adverse impacts, including by strengthening their resilience, and take action for their restoration in order to achieve healthy and productive oceans, and: (14.5) By 2020, conserve at least 10 percent of coastal and marine areas, consistent with national and international law and based on the best scientific information available. One of the indicators is the percentage increase in area under mangroves. The latest SDG Index Baseline Report 2024 shows that Karnataka has achieved the highest increase in mangrove cover and has achieved high scores for other indicators along with Andhra Pradesh and Odisha, but West Bengal is an overall achiever of SDG14 targets (NITI Aayog, 2024). Front runners with average scores are Kerala, Maharashtra, Goa and Tamil Nadu. Meanwhile, Gujarat has been classified as an "aspirant" with a decrease in mangrove areas. India's action plans for SDG14 do not specifically highlight other blue carbon ecosystems – saltmarsh and seagrass meadows.

The Ramsar Convention on Wetlands of International Importance is an international treaty that provides a framework for the conservation and wise use of wetlands and their resources. India joined the Convention in 1982, and the implementation of its framework is overseen by the Wetlands Division of the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change. This division manages the

Wetlands of India Portal, which provides regular reports and maps related to wetland management. Currently, India has 85 Ramsar sites, covering a total area of 1,358,066 hectares.

India's national policies and legislation

Our policy assessment revealed that among the 31 assessed national policies (n=11) and pieces of legislation (n=20), mangroves are the most recognised blue carbon ecosystem (Figure 13). Wetlands appear in nine documents, but the term is often used broadly, without specifying particular habitats, and includes both inland and freshwater wetlands. Seagrass is acknowledged in six documents, while saltmarshes are referenced in only four.

Most Indian national policies and legislation recognise the importance of adaptation, biodiversity, and the ecosystem services provided by blue carbon ecosystems. However, only four specifically emphasise their role in climate change mitigation.

All three blue carbon ecosystems are recognised in the National Wildlife Action Plan (2017) for their benefits related to adaptation, biodiversity, and ecosystem services (Figure 13). Additionally, they are acknowledged in the Coastal Regulation Zone Notification (1991) and the Island Coastal Regulation Zone Notification (2019). The Coastal Regulation Zone (CRZ) Notification (1991) emphasises the adaptation benefits of these ecosystems and highlights seagrass meadows as carbon sinks. However, it does not recognise the capacity of the other blue carbon ecosystems to act as carbon sinks. Under the CRZ Notification, coastal areas are divided into four coastal regulation zones– CRZ I, CRZ II, CRZ III and CRZ IV. The CRZ I are ecologically sensitive areas and include mangroves and 50 m buffer areas for mangroves exceeding 1000 km², seagrass meadows, saltmarshes and other coastal habitats.

Most policies and legislation recognise the importance of adaptation, biodiversity, and the ecosystem services provided by blue carbon ecosystems. However, only four specifically emphasise their role in climate change mitigation. Among these are the abovementioned Coastal Regulation Zone Notification (1991) and the Island Coastal Regulation Zone Notification (2019). Additionally, mangrove restoration and conservation are included in the Green Credit Programme established by the Framework for Voluntary Carbon Market in the Agriculture Sector (2024). The significance of mangroves in carbon sequestration and their benefits for adaptation are also highlighted in the Long-Term Low-Carbon Development Strategy (2022).

The Indian Forest Act (1927), the Wildlife (Protection) Act (1972), The Forest Conservation Act (1980) and The Environment (Protection) Act (1986) all can be applied to ensure the conservation and restoration of mangrove ecosystems, although none of them explicitly mention mangroves.

State level legislation

We reviewed 66 state-level policies and legislation. Mangroves were the most mentioned type of blue carbon ecosystem, recognising their adaptation, biodiversity and ecosystem services

State-level policies and legislation include the State Action Plans on Climate Change, State Marine Fishing Regulation Acts and State Forests Acts. Blue carbon ecosystems are not explicitly mentioned in state-level legislation and their mitigation potential is only recognised in one reviewed policy.

benefits (Figure 14). The only reference to the mitigation benefits of blue carbon ecosystems however, is found in the State Action Plan on Climate Change for Andhra Pradesh (2012). State Action Plans on Climate Change (SAPCC) are instrumental in operationalising objectives and missions of the National Action Plan for Climate Change (NAPCC). Seagrass restoration was acknowledged in the Tamil Nadu State Environment Policy 2017, but saltmarsh was not highlighted in any legislation on a state level. None of the Forest Acts or Marine Fisheries Regulations directly mentioned mangroves or seagrass habitats, respectively.

Policy assessment

Although blue carbon ecosystems are not explicitly addressed in many relevant policies and legislation, policy opportunities for including them exist, yet may require further evaluation. We assessed all the policies and legislation for their potential to include blue carbon ecosystems for adaptation, mitigation and biodiversity benefits. The greatest potential for recognising and referencing blue carbon ecosystems for mitigation lies in policies and reports within international frameworks, such as Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) (see Figure 14). A more detailed assessment is necessary to integrate blue carbon ecosystems into national policies and legislation. Most state policies and legislation were assessed as not relevant, primarily because each state has its own version of acts under national laws. For more information on the inclusion of blue carbon ecosystems concerning adaptation and biodiversity, refer to Figures 2A and 3A in Annex A.

Figure 14: Assessment of India's policies and legislation for their potential to incorporate blue carbon for mitigation using a traffic light system.

Blue carbon ecosystem management programmes and initiatives -

National programmes

As part of the National Adaptation Plan to Climate Change (NAPCC), the National Coastal Mission Scheme aims to address the impact of climate change on coastal and

India has several national government-led programmes, plans and projects that aim to conserve, restore and monitor blue carbon ecosystems and increase the resilience of coastal communities benefitting from these ecosystems.

marine ecosystems, infrastructure and communities in coastal areas and support restoration of coastal habitats. The implementing agencies of the National Coastal Mission are the State Governments of Coastal States and Union Territory Administrations. One of the components of the National Coastal Mission is the Management Action Plan on Conservation of Mangroves and Coral Reefs, which includes the Mangrove Initiative for Shoreline Habitats and Tangible Income (MISHTI) (MoEFCC, 2025). It is a government-led initiative to increase the mangrove cover along the coastline and on saltpan lands. It primarily focuses on the Indian Sundarbans and the Hooghly Estuary, but other parts of the country are also considered. The programme is co-ordinated by the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change and funded by the Compensatory Afforestation Fund Management and Planning Authority (CAMPA), the Mahatma Gandhi National Employment Rural Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS) and other sources. It is part of the National Coastal Mission Scheme (under NAPCC), specifically the Conservation and Management of Mangroves and Coral Reef programme (MoEFCC, 2022b). The Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change is also leading a project called ECRICC: Enhancing Climate Resilience of India's Coastal Communities. It aims to enhance the resilience of the lives and livelihoods of the most vulnerable populations, particularly women, in the coastal areas of India to climate change and extreme events in all coastal states and Union Territories. This six-year project deploys an ecosystem-centred and community-based approach and reports to have already restored 2,475 ha of mangroves, 500 ha of saltmarsh and protected and restored 85 ha of seagrass meadows (ECRICC, 2025).

Another route to support blue carbon ecosystem conservation and restoration is Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM). From 2010, The World Bank has been assisting the Government of India in building national capacity to implement a comprehensive coastal management approach and piloting the integrated coastal zone management approach in three states - Gujarat, Orissa and West Bengal. The audit carried out by the World Bank (2020) showed satisfactory outcomes. Consequently, project ENCORE builds upon the above-mentioned ICZM project to strengthen integrated coastal zone management in other Coastal States and Union Territories of India (The World Bank, 2019). By recognising the linkages between coastal conservation, climate resilience, and poverty reduction and by building the collective capacity of communities and decentralised governments, it aims to enhance coastal resilience and coastal resource efficiency. The project acknowledges all blue carbon ecosystems and their provided ecosystem services.

India also has mechanisms in place to evaluate the success of coastal ecosystem conservation efforts. In 2022 the Comptroller and Auditor General of India released the Performance Audit on Conservation of Coastal Ecosystems for the period from 2015 to 2020. This audit examined the activities, clearances and monitoring as required per CRZ Notification, the success of objectives of

the ICZM Programme and the measures taken up by the Government towards achieving the targets under SDG 14 (Comptroller and Auditor General of India, 2022). The report provides a detailed account of the successes and failures of all of these points but highlighted the ongoing anthropogenic impacts such as pollution and development, on coastal areas that are identified as Ecologically Sensitive Areas.

Research projects and community-lead initiatives

East Coast

In West Bengal, conservation and restoration efforts are primarily focused on the Sundarban mangrove forest. One notable project is led by the NGO Nature Environment and Wildlife Society (NEWS) and is supported by the Livelihoods Funds (Figure 15,

The benefits of conservation and restoration of blue carbon ecosystems, particularly mangroves, have been well acknowledged by communities and research institutes across India. Below are some selected examples of India's blue carbon ecosystem conservation, restoration and monitoring projects.

[1]). Established in 2011, this initiative has worked with local communities to plant over 16 million mangrove trees. It recognises the various ecosystem services these mangroves provide, including flood and storm protection, biodiversity enhancement, livelihood support, and carbon sequestration and storage (Livelihoods-NEWS, 2025). The Indian Sundarbans mangrove project is another example of a successful project which resulted in the planting of over 5600 ha of mangroves, with three times more carbon sequestration than predicted highlighted in the literature review (Figure 15, [2]) (Wylie et al., 2016). Another area that has received attention is Sagar Island. The Sagar Island Mangrove Reforestation Project aims to restore 10 hectares of land by planting 200,000 mangrove trees (The Good Idea, 2023) (Figure 15 [3]).

Odisha is one of the states that benefits from the ECRICC: Enhancing Climate Resilience of India's Coastal Communities project. The primary focus of mangrove conservation and restoration is the Bhitarkanika National Park (Figure 15, [4]) (UNDP, 2019; ECRICC, 2025). It is a Ramsar site and mainland India's second-largest mangrove forest. These mangroves have been under pressure from natural hazards, including cyclones, and human activities, such as deforestation for fuel wood and agriculture (Chilika Development Authority, 2023). Researchers from the National Centre for Sustainable Coastal Management and other institutions with the Forest Department of Odisha are surveying and mapping the area to identify the most suitable mangrove restoration sites (Chilika Development Authority, 2023). Chilika also has the second largest seagrass meadows in India, and while most research focus is on the seagrass meadows in Palk Bay and the Gulf of Mannar, Tamil Nadu, conservation and restoration measures are in place in Chilika (Acharyya et al., 2023) (Figure 15, [5]).

Figure 15: Distribution of research and community-led initiatives in India.

Both seagrass and mangrove habitats are restored and protected in Andhra Pradesh, including a seagrass restoration project led by four students from Dr Lankapalli Bullaya College in Visakhapatnam (Peri, 2024) (Figure 15, [6]). The Mangrove Ecosystem Conservation and Restoration (MECR) programme, led by the Forest Department in collaboration with the TREE Foundation and local fishing communities, aims to restore and conserve vital mangrove ecosystems along the coast of Andhra Pradesh. The MECR programme seeks to protect biodiversity, support sustainable livelihoods, and restore degraded coastal landscapes while also mitigating climate change (Annam, 2024). The project engages with fishermen and other local stakeholders through awareness programmes, hands-on training, and capacity-building workshops to protect and conserve mangroves outside protected areas. As part of the MECR programme, the existing mangroves on revenue lands are surveyed and mapped, and the degraded areas suitable for restoration are prepared for plantation after all required permissions have been obtained. The project has already successfully planted over 1,760 mangrove saplings in Nellore and Prakasam districts (Figure 15, [7]).

In Tamil Nadu, the Organization for Marine Conservation, Awareness and Research (OMCAR) is leading seagrass and mangrove protection and restoration projects in Palk Bay and the wider Southeast Coast (MANGREEN project) by collaborating with local fishing communities and the government (OMCAR, 2025) (Figure 15, [8]). Seagrass meadows in the Gulf of Mannar and Palk Bay are essential habitats for the endangered dugongs. Thus, the Suganthi Devadason Marine Research Institute (SDMRI), affiliated with the Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, also restores seagrass habitats, acknowledging their carbon sequestration and storage benefits (Dass, 2021) (Figure 15, [9]).

West Coast

In Kerala, most mangroves are privately owned wetlands, making conservation and restoration difficult. In recent years, the Forest Department has initiated reclassifying these lands as forests and acquiring them from private owners (Menon et al., 2023). A project undertaken by the Wildlife Trust of India in 2006 called Kannur Kandal Project (kandal means mangrove in Malayalam) has purchased 37 acres of privately owned mangroves (Figure 15, [10]). These purchases have been supported by World Land Trust (WLT), Apollo Tyres, IFAW, SBI Foundation and other independent donors (WTI, 2025). The long-term plan is to secure 100 acres of such mangrove lands in the Kannur district to establish a mangrove conservation model, a Mother (main) nursery and at least five satellite nurseries to facilitate mangrove restoration in the district. In 2024, WTI extended this project to Cheruthazham Grama Panchayath, where the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) has involved the local community, in particular, women, to restore 4 acres by planting 10000 mangrove saplings of 2 different species (WTI, 2024) (Figure 15, [11]). In January 2025, the Buimerc Foundation, in collaboration with the M.S. Swaminathan Research Foundation (MSSRF), launched a three-year mangrove restoration project for the Kerala coast (The Hindu, 2025). The pilot programme will include restoration along the Vypeen coast and the development of 20,000 saplings for planting and distribution to places facing a shortage of saplings (Figure 15, [12]). The project also aims to raise awareness, build the capacity and skills of young people, develop a field nursery, plant saplings and monitor their growth.

In Karnataka, mangrove restoration projects are mainly undertaken by local community groups and non-profit organisations supported by forest divisions. In 2012, researchers from the Environmental Information System [ENVIS] Centre for Ecological Sciences, Indian Institute of Science identified mangrove areas for restoration and conservation in Uttara Kannada district (Subash Chandran et al., 2012) (Figure 15, [13]). Since then, small-scale conservation and conservation projects have been implemented in Karwar and Honnavar (Yadav, 2021) (Figure 15, [14]).

Figure 16: MANGREEN mangrove restoration (credit left: Society for Ecological Restoration (credit right: Deepwave.org)

Figure 17: Harvesters near the Gulf of Kutch, Jamnagar (credit: Shrutika Parihar)

livelihood-based activities and mangrove restoration (UNDP, 2024) (Figure 15, [16]). These efforts have led to the establishment of livelihood groups focused on crab farming and the implementation of measures to protect the mangroves. In 2021, the Applied Environmental Research Foundation (AERF) was awarded a grant by Apple to protect mangroves by creating alternative, sustainable industries in the local communities that cultivate and benefit from the biodiversity and resilience of the mangrove ecosystems (Apple, 2022) (Figure 15, [17]). There are also resident-led initiatives, such as Shree Ekvira Aai Pratishthan, involving fishermen to help restore mangroves and wetlands (Pathak, 2019) (Figure 15, [18]).

Goa's mangroves are set to be restored as part of national programs like MISHTI. Additionally, there are several local conservation and restoration initiatives underway. One such initiative is the Goa Mangrove Community Art Collective, which aims to raise awareness about mangroves and their benefits. Their first project entitled "Aamche Mangrove" operates at the intersection of citizen science, conservation, awareness and art (Figure 15, [15]). This initiative not only seeks to build awareness but also to create an emotional connection with mangroves, fostering positive action for their conservation (D'Silva, 2022).

In Maharashtra, projects focused on mangrove conservation and restoration often emphasise the importance of these ecosystems in providing livelihoods for local communities. For instance, a project aimed at improving the climate resilience of local communities in Navghar, supported by the Government of India, UNDP, and the Green Climate Fund, has trained women's self-help groups in

There are initiatives for all three coastal habitat types in Gujarat. The Rann of Kutch Seasonal Salt Marsh is a salt flat in the dry season, but the monsoon rains transform the area into a saltmarsh teeming with wildlife. The area also includes estuaries, brackish lagoons, tidal mudflats, and permanent saline marshes. It is one of WWF's Global 200 ecoregions — a science-based global ranking of the world's most biologically outstanding habitats. WWF-India is now working to design the Rann of Kutch as a Ramsar Site that would help with conservation efforts (Wikramanayake, 2020) (Figure 15, [19]).

Seagrass habitats are essential for dugongs. Therefore, projects such as CAMPA - Recovery of dugongs and their habitat in India also map, monitor and restore seagrass habitats. The Gulf of Kutch in Gujarat is one of the areas this project focuses on (Wildlife Institute of India, 2020) (Figure 15, [20]); others include the Andaman and Nicobar Islands and the Gulf of Mannar and Palk Bay in Tamil Nadu. The project actively involves school children, students and fishers. The Gulf of Kutch region also has extensive mangroves, and the Gujarat State Forest Department and Gujarat Ecology Commission have facilitated a community-based mangrove restoration. Reforestation across participating villages in Gujarat resulted in 8,326 ha of new mangrove cover (NbS Initiative, 2025) (Figure 15, [21]). Residents have reported benefits, such as reducing the negative impacts of cyclones and increasing income from fisheries. These are just a few examples of various initiatives in the region.

Union Territories

In the Lakshadweep Islands and Andaman and Nicobar Islands, monitoring, conservation and restoration efforts focus on seagrass habitats. Researchers and non-profit environmental organisations are particularly interested in the impact of green sea turtles on these habitats. They are monitoring the population of green sea turtles to assess their role in overgrazing seagrass in the lagoons of Lakshadweep (Gangal et al., 2021) (Figure 15, [22]). Singh et al. (2024) monitored post 2004 tsunami mangrove colonisation in isolated uplifted reef beds in North Andaman, highlighting the unique opportunity of post-disturbance recovery (Figure 15, [23]). Mangrove conservation is also taking place but on a more localised basis. Andaman and Nicobar Islands are one of the sites of the Center for International Forestry Research and World Agroforestry (CIFOR-ICRAF) mangrove monitoring programme [Figure 15, [24]]. Supported by the US Forest

Figure 18: Fisher near Andaman and Nicobar Islands (credit: Nabil Naidu, via Unsplash)

Service and several other collaborators, CIFOR-ICRAF is setting up long-term monitoring plots to study the sedimentation rate, salinity and tidal changes and estimate the aboveground and belowground biomass at select sites across India. Other current sites include the Sundarbans in West Bengal and the Coringa Wildlife Sanctuary in Andhra Pradesh, with future work planned in Odisha, Karnataka, Maharashtra and Gujarat (CIFOR-ICRAF, 2025).

PART 2 – Gap Analysis

It is evident from a review of the literature that blue carbon is becoming increasingly of interest in the Indian science community. While some topics and regions have received large amounts of attention, there is room for growth and expansion of research. Further, there is great potential, particularly at the national level, for blue carbon to become a prominent consideration in coastal and marine policy discussions. Based on the outcomes of the literature review and policy scan presented above, seven gaps have been identified as areas for further work, in order of priority.

Figure 19: Seven gaps in blue carbon science and policy identified in this review.

Gap 1 – Habitat Mapping: While mangrove ecosystems are well surveyed in India, there is limited data available on the distribution of seagrass meadows and saltmarshes, and even less data regarding their health and blue carbon potential.

Gap 2 – Blue Carbon Mitigation Potential: The benefits of mangrove habitats, in particular, are recognised in India for biodiversity and climate change adaptation. However, the climate change mitigation potential of all blue carbon ecosystems is not fully recognised in national and state policies and legislation.

Gap 3 – Measurement Methodologies: There is a wealth of valuable blue carbon data available in India. In order to generate accurate measurements of carbon stocks, a consistent methodology is required, which includes standardised methods in line with IPCC requirements, as well as methods to bring existing stock data in line with these reporting requirements.

Gap 4 – Blue Carbon Stock Take: Carbon stocks, greenhouse gas emissions, and related blue carbon assessment data are increasingly available for mangroves, however these data are incomplete for saltmarshes and seagrass meadows. There is also limited data on total (aboveground, belowground, and soil) carbon stocks for all blue carbon ecosystems across India.

Gap 5 – Impacts of Climate Change: There is a growing understanding of the significance of climate change across India, however limited attention has been given to these impacts (including sea level rise, drought, etc.) on blue carbon potential.

Gap 6 – Geographical Distribution of Research: The spatial coverage of blue carbon research across India is growing, but this research is concentrated in a few highly studied regions (e.g., the Sundarbans and Bhitarkanika) and does not expand equally to other blue-carbon rich areas.

Gap 7 – Restoration and Monitoring: There has been significant interest in mangrove conservation and restoration, but there is still limited focus on seagrass and saltmarsh habitat restoration and monitoring.

Figure 20: Chilika Lake, home to an estimate 8000ha of seagrass meadows in India (credit: Mystery Cat, Unsplash).

PART 3 – Science and Policy Evidence Needs and Opportunities

Evidence Needs

Based on the gaps identified above, the following evidence needs have been established. Each of these needs responds to either one or more of the gaps highlighted above. In many cases, these evidence needs build on each other and some actions need to be completed before others can take place. Figure 22 depicts the timeframe (short-term, medium-term, or long-term) over which

the authors recommend that each of these could be acted on to meet future science and policy objectives across India.

Short-term (1-3+ years):

Evidence Need 1 – Habitat mapping to provide a country-wide understanding of blue carbon ecosystem extent.

Responds to: Gap 1 (Habitat Mapping), Gap 2 (Blue Carbon Mitigation Potential), & Gap 6 (Geographical Distribution of Research)

Evidence Need 2 – Feasibility assessment for incorporating blue carbon ecosystems into federal and state policies.

Responds to: Gap 2 (Blue Carbon Mitigation Potential)

Evidence Need 3 – Standardised methods and quality control to allow for direct comparison of stocks across India, and to align Indian blue carbon stock measurements with global values.

Responds to: Gap 3 (Measurement Methodologies) & Gap 4 (Blue Carbon Stock Take)

Medium-term (1-5+ years):

Evidence Need 4 – Country-wide carbon stock (aboveground, belowground, and soil) assessments for mangrove, seagrass and saltmarsh habitats.

Responds to: Gap 4 (Blue Carbon Stock Take)

Long-term (1-10+ years):

Evidence Need 5 – Data on presence, health, and sequestration potential of blue carbon ecosystems in states where few publications have emerged (see Figure 10).

Responds to: Gap 6 (Geographical Distribution of Research)

Evidence Need 6 – Greater understanding of the impacts of climate change in blue carbon ecosystems to appropriately protect these ecosystems in the future.

Responds to: Gap 5 (Impacts of Climate Change)

Evidence Need 7 – Greater understanding of how to effectively restore seagrass and saltmarsh habitats across different sites.

Responds to: Gap 7 (Restoration and Monitoring)

Figure 21: This figure depicts the recommended time frames (short-, medium-, and long-term) associated with fulfilling each Evidence Need, including which gap is being addressed by each Evidence Need.

Opportunities

This literature review and gap analysis have revealed potential opportunities for strengthening the role of blue carbon in the science and policy communities in India, including through partnership with the UK. However, further efforts would be needed to ensure that these solutions are equitable, practical, and implementable within the vastly different regions into which they might be put in place. In line with recommendations and current policies of the Ministry of Environment, Forestry and Climate Change of India, the focus should be on **protecting** existing carbon stores, enhancing sequestration by **restoring** degraded habitats and **creating** new habitats in suitable areas. Below we identify four major opportunity areas for the UK to support India in achieving these objectives, with suggested actions for operationalising these opportunities.

Opportunity Area 1 – A Collaborative Science Forum: Development of a country-wide programme that brings in expertise across the sectors, including earth scientists, ocean scientists, natural scientists, social scientists, policymakers, and community members, to develop a research protocol that responds to the science gaps identified in the report. This could involve:

- **Action 1.1:** The development of standardised methods and quality control for blue carbon stock measurements. Existing partnerships with UK-based blue carbon experts with experience designing blue carbon sampling protocols including national scale citizen science initiatives could inform this process as needed.
- **Action 1.2:** Resources to support nationwide mapping, monitoring, and successful restoration of mangroves, seagrass meadows and saltmarshes, including training workshops and research exchanges. Collaborations could be made between Indian and UK restoration practitioners which build on existing methodologies have been developed for seagrass restoration in India. Create accessible restoration handbooks using Seagrass Restoration and Saltmarsh Restoration Handbooks developed by the Environment Agency in the UK as examples and translate them into local languages.
- **Action 1.3:** An India-wide seagrass mapping effort collaboration between National Centre for Coastal Research (NCCR) and UK scientists. There have already been subtidal ecosystem mapping pilot projects in progress, including using satellite videos and drones to determine what equipment or technology is most suitable to seagrass mapping based on trials with corals in Lakshadweep. This could also benefit methodology development for seagrass mapping in the UK, where improvement is needed as well.
- **Action 1.4:** An India-wide saltmarsh mapping and carbon assessment effort. In India, saltmarshes are among the least studied blue carbon ecosystems. The UK has developed the UK Saltmarsh Code which could serve as a valuable example for unlocking the potential of saltmarshes in providing mitigation benefits and strengthen their role in carbon markets.

Opportunity Area 2 – Development of a Blue Carbon Inventory for India informed by global efforts and ongoing work in the UK: Recent efforts in the UK to establish a national blue carbon roadmap and evidence needs partnerships could be adapted to an Indian context to support a nation-wide blue carbon stock take. An evidence needs partnership would aid the identification of evidence gaps beyond those identified in this report and develop methods to fill those gaps, by leveraging the expertise of all partners and shaping collaboration in a way that prioritises shared objectives. This could involve:

- **Action 2.1:** Working towards the potential inclusion of mangroves, saltmarsh and seagrass in India's Greenhouse Gas Inventory and Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC).
- **Action 2.2:** Both formal and informal on-the-ground research partnerships with academics from the UK and India could create to support this government-to-government opportunity.

Opportunity Area 3 – Weaving Blue Carbon Ecosystems into National and State Policies: The policy scan introduced above provides a great foundation for exploring how blue carbon could be further woven into national and state policies to achieve climate change mitigation, adaptation, and biodiversity benefits. Existing programmes such as the Mangrove Initiative for Shoreline Habitats and Tangible Income (MISHTI) and India Global Environment Facility Coastal and Marine Program (IGCMP) emphasise the importance of mangroves. However, saltmarshes and seagrass meadows remain largely neglected. These initiatives primarily focus on specific states such as Andhra Pradesh and West Bengal, highlighting the need for a national effort to support all states and union territories, especially those with more fragmented blue carbon habitats. Additionally, a shared government-to-government understanding of the opportunities of these policies on the ground is needed. These efforts could support:

- **Action 3.1:** Managing coastal and marine habitats on a seascape scale, with consideration of land and marine connectivity.
- **Action 3.2:** Reducing the impacts of human and environmental pressures on blue carbon ecosystems, enhancing the capacity of these ecosystems to act as nature-based solutions which would in turn increase the resilience of coastal communities to climate change.
- **Action 3.3:** Further assessment of relevant policies (see Figure 22 for potential policy opportunities) to legally strengthen the protection and restoration of blue carbon ecosystems.

Opportunity Area 4– Emerging carbon and nature markets: Carbon markets could offer significant opportunities to finance blue carbon restoration projects, which often lack support from other funding sources. Organisations such as the Energy and Resources Institute (TERI) are beginning to draw upon these opportunities in some regions, but there are opportunities to expand this work across larger scales and regions to create nation-wide interlinked markets. Addressing the financial gap while ensuring these projects deliver multiple benefits could be achieved by:

- **Action 4.1:** Collaborations with public and private sector organisations to expand assessments of capacity for blue carbon ecosystems to play a role in carbon markets.
- **Action 4.2:** Encouraging and enabling investment and public-private partnership in blue carbon initiatives at the regional and national scale that provide multiple benefits to local communities.
- **Action 4.3:** Developing a carbon credit system that is suitable for India's context and values the engagement of local communities with support from the UK, drawing on its experience in climate financing.
- **Action 4.4:** Assessing how blue carbon projects align with community values and what is required to enable their participation in these projects, including integrating local and Indigenous knowledge. Creating regulations that ensure that communities benefit from carbon credits in India's complex land ownership landscape.

- Assessed as highly relevant for mitigation potential
- Assessed as relevant for mitigation but requires further assessment
- None of the blue carbon ecosystems are currently included for mitigation
- Not all blue carbon ecosystems are acknowledged - extend to all ecosystems for mitigation
- All blue carbon ecosystems are included for their biodiversity benefits
- Assessed as highly relevant for adaptation or biodiversity
- Assessed as relevant for adaptation or biodiversity but requires further assessment

★ Different states may include different blue carbon ecosystems, or might not include them at all

★ Not all policies were available in each state; therefore, we assessed a few examples, but the opportunities remain the same for all coastal states

Figure 22: Policy opportunities for including blue carbon ecosystems for their mitigation, adaptation and biodiversity benefits in India's national and state-level policies and legislation and policies and reporting required by international policy frameworks. For a more detailed assessment, please refer to Table 4A in Annex A.

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Annex A: Supplementary tables and figures

Table 1A : Soil organic carbon stock in mangroves, seagrass, and saltmarshes in India (all stock values reported as MgC/ha – rows are greyed out where conversions have been made).

Blue carbon ecosystem	Location	Soil Organic Carbon Stock (MgC(t)/ha)	StD	Core depth (cm)	Ref
Mangrove	South Andaman Islands	307.02	103.93	100	(Ragavan et al., 2023)
	Carbyn's Cove	248.18	38.63		
	Bedonabad	375.51	118.9		
	Burmanallah 1	318.39	55.75		
	Burmanallah 2	430.17	55.04		
	Chedyatapu	431.83	16.77		
	Guptapara	246.73	143.88		
	Majery	298.32	27.07		
	Munroe Island	13.72	2.26	100	(Sreelekshmi et al., 2022)
	Ayiramthengu	14.96	3.75		
	Vypin	36.99	20.73		
	Pichavaram Site 1	146.1	-	0-90	(Gnanamoorthy et al., 2019)
	Pichavaram Site 2	99.29	-		
	Pichavaram Site 3	93.18	-		
	Pichavaram Site 4	57.41	-		
	Pichavaram Site 5	95.54	-		
	Pichavaram Site 6	84.84	-		
	Matlapalem	115	-	42	(Rao et al., 2022)
	Coringa Site 1	189	-	92	
	Coringa Site 2	195	-	80	
	Gaderu Site 1	181	-	80	
	Gaderu Site 2	131	-	100	
	Gaderu Site 3	135	-	150	
	Dangmal	6.68	0.47	1-5	(Banerjee et al., 2021)
	Bhitarkanika	7.71	0.45		
	Gupti	5.83	0.24		
	Habalikhathi	3.52	0.12		
	Ekakula	3.55	0.11		
	Jambu	3.61	0.3		
	Kansaridia	7.55	0.56		
	Kandarapatia	7.71	0.45		
	Kantilo	5.36	0.29		
	Bhitar Kharnasi	5.39	0.25		

	Bichitrapur Mangrove Sanctuary, Odisha (dense mangrove)	306.88	106.52	100	(Dey et al., 2024)
	Dadanpatra, West Bengal (open degraded mangrove)	44.47	20.37		
	Vypin Island	18.26	3.9	30	(ShyleshChandran et al., 2020)
	Thalassery estuary	17.48	7.3	N/A	(Vinod et al., 2020)
	Bichitrapur Mangrove Sanctuary, Odisha (entire forest, estimate)	125.5586	-	100	(Datta et al., 2022) <i>*Originally reported as Mg</i>
	Mahanadi Mangrove Wetland (mean of natural mangrove stands)	54.3	7.4	30	(Sahu et al., 2016)
	Mahanadi Mangrove Wetland (mean of mangrove plantation)	60.9	13.9		
	Sundarbans Biosphere Reserve (extrapolated from Henry, Jharkhali, & Jhingakhali)	61.4122	-	90	(Barik et al., 2021) <i>*Originally reported as Tg</i>
	Bhitarkanika Conservation Area (scrub mangrove)	177	14	185, 162, 189	(Bhomia et al., 2016)
	Bhitarkanika Conservation Area (planted mangrove)	92	20	98	
	Bhitarkanika Conservation Area (dense mangrove)	134	17	138 and 112	
	Kochi Mangroves (average)	73.22	39.4	30	(Rani et al., 2023)
	Mangalavanam Bird Sanctuary	118.45			
	Kadalundi	63.87	8.67	30	(Vinod et al., 2018)
	Tuna Creek, Gulf of Kutch	32.02	-	100	(Sigamani et al., 2023)
	Phane Creek, Gulf of Kutch	27.1	-		
	Kandla Creek, Gulf of Kutch	25.84	-		
	Jangi Creek, Gulf of Kutch	20.52	-		

	Navalkhi Creek, Gulf of Kutch	23.86	-		
	Gulf of Kutch	25.87	-		
	Bhitarkanika Wildlife Sanctuary (average)	3.73	2.1	10	(Bal & Banerjee, 2019)
Seagrass	Swaraj Dweep	7.2332	-	10	(Mishra et al., 2023) <i>*Originally reported as MgC</i>
	Shaheed Dweep	13.0004	-		
	Burmanallah	7.0197	-		
	Venadu Site 1	6.55	0.1	Between 100 and 150	(Murugan et al., 2024)
	Venadu Site 2	11.9	0.84		
	Pantrangam	1.29	0.2		
	Erukkam (Irukkam)	2.78	0.1		
	Palk Bay (averaged)	0.34472	-	20	(Kaladharan et al., 2020) <i>*Originally reported as gC/ha</i>
	Gulf of Mannar (averaged)	3.885615	-		
	Pulicat Lake (averaged)	0.998	0.418	30	(Kaladharan et al., 2021)
	Chilika Lake (averaged)	2.018	0.673		
	Andaman and Nicobar (average)	184.24	23.84	N/A	(Stankovic et al., 2021)
	Chilika Lake (averaged over species at Chilika Lake and Palk Bay)	129	-	100	(Ganguly et al., 2018)
	Palk Bay (averaged over species at Chilika Lake and Palk Bay)	129	-		
	Pamban/Mandapam North (dry season)	84.79	1.37	30	(Ranith et al., 2024)
	Devipattinam/Thondi (dry season)	136.22	8.38		
Saltmarsh	Tuticorin (dry)	8.42	0.64	30	(Kaviarasan et al., 2019)
	Tuticorin (wet)	54.46	1.64		
	Dangmal	48.07	1.21	10	(Banerjee et al., 2022b)
	Bhitarkanika	55.54	1.32		
	Gupti	41.97	1.17		
	Habalikhathi	30.08	1.09		
	Ekakula	30.47	1.1		
	Jambu	25.99	0.23		
	Kansaridia	54.35	0.22		
	Kandarapatia	55.51	0.24		
	Kantilo	38.61	0.26		
	Kharinasi	38.79	0.2		

Table 2A: Vegetation carbon stock in mangroves, seagrass, and saltmarshes in India.

Blue carbon ecosystem	Location	Vegetation Carbon Stock (MgC/ha)	StD	Ref	
Mangrove	Kerala	194.03	177.51	(Sreelekshmi et al., 2022)	
	South Andaman	213.63	40.59	(Ragavan et al., 2023)	
	Baratang Island	203.91	53.57		
	Middle Andaman	349.85	53.56		
	North Andaman	351.82	72.21		
	Little Andaman	494.50	194.56		
	Havelock	299.87	53.50		
	Entire Andaman Islands	290.26	24.75		
	Bhitarkanika (planted mangrove)	7	4	(Bhomia et al., 2016)	
	Bhitarkanika (scrub mangrove)	65	11		
	Bhitarkanika (dense mangrove)	100	11		
	Mangrove	Tuna Creek, Gulf of Kutch	45.1		(Sigamani et al., 2023)
		Phane Creek, Gulf of Kutch	41.3		
		Kandla Creek, Gulf of Kutch	25.3		
Jangi Creek, Gulf of Kutch		25.2			
Navalkhi Creek, Gulf of Kutch		133.9			
Gulf of Kutch		54.1			
Seagrass	Venadu Site 1	0.49	0.07	(Murugan et al., 2024) *recorded as "species carbon"	
	Venadu Site 2	3.48	0.16		
	Pantrangam	9.52	0.63		
	Erukkam (Irukkam)	1.02	0.06		

Table 3A: Total ecosystem organic carbon stock in mangroves, seagrass, and saltmarshes in India. (all stock values reported as MgC/ha – rows are greyed out where conversions have been made).

Blue carbon ecosystem	Location	Total ecosystem organic carbon Stock (MgC/ha)	StD	Ref
Mangrove	Kerala	218.98	169.86	(Sreelekshmi et al., 2022)

	Dangmal	69.11	17.43	(Banerjee et al., 2021)
	Bhitarkanika	322.47	110.79	
	Gupti	117.42	22.21	
	Habalikhathi	137.48	22.24	
	Ekakula	61.33	12.38	
	Jambu	87.00	16.04	
	Kansaridia	73.40	17.46	
	Kandarapatia	77.73	21.22	
	Kantilo	181.55	42.42	
	Bhitar Kharnasi	51.35	6.77	
	Bichitrapur Mangrove Sanctuary, Odisha (restored)	182.68	-	(Dey et al., 2024) <i>*originally reported as Mg</i>
	Dadanpatra, West Bengal (degraded)	93.64	-	
	Thalassery Estuary	153.64	-	(Vinod et al., 2020)
	Mahanadi (natural mangrove stand)	143.4	8.2	(Sahu et al., 2016)
	Mahanadi (plantation mangrove stand)	151.5	7.9	
	Bhitarkanika (planted mangrove)	104.16	-	(Bhomia et al., 2016) <i>*Originally reported as Tg</i>
	Bhitarkanika (scrub mangrove)	246.24	-	
	Bhitarkanika (dense mangrove)	234.21	-	
	Kochi	335.33	184.47	(Rani et al., 2023)
	Aroor	280.46	-	
	Malippuram	184.52	-	
	Mangalavanam Bird Sanctuary	182.15	-	
	Kadalundi	182.15	-	(Vinod et al., 2018)
Seagrass	Andaman and Nicobar	6.87	-	(Mishra et al., 2023) <i>*Originally reported as Mg</i>
	Andaman and Nicobar	184.24	23.84	(Stankovic et al., 2021)
Saltmarsh	Bhitarkanika	49.58	2.46	(Banerjee et al., 2022a)
	Mahanadi	49.73	1.38	

Figure 1A: Box and whisker plot showing variations in soil (shades of brown), vegetation (shades of blue), and total organic carbon (shades of green) in mangroves (darkest shades), seagrasses (medium shades), and saltmarshes (lightest shades) in India. Boxes represent the interquartile range (25th to 75th percentile), the line within the interquartile range shows the median, and the “x” denotes the mean. Whiskers show the minimum and maximum values calculated as 1.5 times the interquartile range above or below the 25th and 75th percentiles. Outliers are only present for mangrove soil organic carbon. Particularly for measurements of soil and total organic carbon, it is noted that soil core depths varied widely across study sites.

Figure 2A. Assessment of India's policies and legislation for their potential to incorporate blue carbon for adaptation using a traffic light system.

Inclusion of the blue carbon ecosystems for biodiversity

Figure 3A. Assessment of India's policies and legislation for their potential to incorporate blue carbon for biodiversity using a traffic light system.

Table 4A. Detailed policy scan of international, national and state-level policies and legislation. This table shows the review of various policies and legislations to determine whether they address blue carbon ecosystems, which include mangroves (MG), saltmarshes (SM), seagrasses (SG), and wetlands (W). For each policy and piece of legislation, we assessed whether blue carbon ecosystems were included (Yes - Y or No - N) and, if applicable, for what purposes (A for adaptation, M for mitigation, B for biodiversity, and ES for other ecosystem services). All policies and legislations were evaluated for their potential contributions to adaptation (A), mitigation (M), or biodiversity (B) benefits. The opportunity assessment was conducted by all three authors.

 = blue carbon ecosystems already included

Title	Type	Responsible entity	Coastal ecosystems covered				Capacity				Relevance			Opportunity
			MG	SM	SG	W *	A	M	B	ES	A	M	B	
POLICIES AND REPORTS UNDER INTERNATIONAL FRAMEWORKS														
Nationally Determined Contributions		Required by UNFCCC. Led by the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change	Y/N **	N	N	N	Y/N **	N	N	N		Blue carbon ecosystems could be included both for mitigation and adaptation, and indirectly for their contribution to support biodiversity.		
National Action Plan for Climate Change (NAPCC) 2008	Policy - NAP equivalent	Required by UNFCCC. Various, but led by the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change.	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N		While Blue carbon ecosystems are covered in schemes under missions, they could be included directly in the NAPCC.		
National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP) (2024-2030)	Policy	Required by the CBD. Led by the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, National Biodiversity Authority		There has been a mention of carbon stocks in the previous versions, thus could be mentioned again in the following ones.										

SDG Index Baseline Report 2024	Report	NITI Aayog				Y			Y					Potential to include mitigation benefits of blue carbon ecosystems under SDG13 Climate Action. Extend to all BCEs for other SDGs such as SDG14 Life below water.
The Fourth Biennial Update Report (BUR-4)		Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N				This could include detailed GHG emissions by Sources and Removals by Sinks estimated for Wetlands.
NATIONAL POLICIES														
Title	Type	Responsible entity	MG	SM	SG	W *	A	M	B	ES	A	M	B	Opportunity
National Environment Policy 2006	Policy	Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y				Extend to seagrass and saltmarsh habitats.
Framework for Voluntary Carbon Market in Agriculture Sector.	Policy	Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N				Currently the restoration and afforestation only extend to mangroves, but green credit programme could include restoration of other wetland habitats.
India's Long-Term Low-Carbon Development Strategy, 2022	Policy	Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N				Extend to seagrass and saltmarsh habitats.
National Mission on Sustainable Habitat (2021-2030).	Policy	Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N				Mangroves and saltmarshes are prominent in some urban coastal areas, therefore there is a strong opportunity to include blue carbon ecosystems for achieving the aims of this mission.
National Disaster Management Plan 2019	Policy	National Disaster Management Authority, Ministry of Home Affairs	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N				Extend to seagrass and saltmarsh habitats.

National Policy on Marine Fisheries 2017.	Policy	Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare (Department of Animal Husbandry, Dairying and Fisheries)	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y				Greater recognition of blue carbon ecosystems and their benefits.
National Wildlife Action Plan, 2017	Policy	Ministry of Environment, Forestry and Climate Change, Wildlife Division	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y				Acknowledge the benefits of restoring seagrass and saltmarsh habitats for wildlife.
Bay of Bengal Large Marine Ecosystem Strategic Action Programme, 2015	Policy	Multi organisation policy, covering 8 countries - India, Bangladesh, Indonesia, Malaysia, Maldives, Myanmar, Sri Lanka, Thailand	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y				Opportunity for recognising their mitigation potential of blue carbon ecosystems.
National Agroforestry Policy, 2014	Policy	Government of India, Ministry of Agriculture, Department of Agriculture & Cooperation.	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of mangroves explicitly.
Comprehensive Marine Fishing Policy 2004.	Policy	Government of India Ministry of Agriculture Department of Animal Husbandry & Dairying	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y				Recognise the benefits of seagrass and mangrove ecosystems for fisheries.
National Forest Policy, 1988.	Policy	Government of India, Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of mangroves explicitly.
NATIONAL LEGISLATION														
Title	Type	Responsible entity	MG	SM	SG	W *	A	M	B	ES	A	M	B	Opportunity
Environment (Protection) Act, 1986 (No. 29 of 1986).	Legislation/Act	Central Government	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of blue carbon ecosystems explicitly.
Environment (Protection) Rules, 1986.	Regulation	Central Government	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of blue carbon ecosystems explicitly.

Environmental Impact Assessment Notification 2006.	Regulation	Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of blue carbon ecosystems explicitly.
The Coastal Regulation Zone Notification, 1991	Law	Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N				Expand mitigation potential to mangroves and saltmarsh.
Notification S.O. 4886(E) of 2021 amending the Coastal Regulation Zone Notification, 2019.	Regulation	Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change	Y	N	N	N	N		N	N				Not relevant - just a notification of amendment
Island Coastal Regulation Zone Notification, 2019.	Regulation	Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N				Expand mitigation potential to mangroves and saltmarsh
The Coastal Aquaculture Authority Act, 2005 (Act No. 24 of 2005).	Legislation	The Coastal Aquaculture Authority, Department of Fisheries, Ministry of Fisheries, Animal Husbandry and Dairy	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - the act establishes the Coastal Aquaculture Authority
Coastal Aquaculture Authority Rules, 2024.	Regulation	The Coastal Aquaculture Authority, Department of Fisheries, Ministry of Fisheries, Animal Husbandry and Dairy	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y				Recognise the benefits of seagrass.
Indian Forest Act, 1927.	Legislation	State Government	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of mangroves explicitly.

The Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980	Legislation	Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of mangroves explicitly.
Compensatory Afforestation Fund Act, 2016 (Act No. 38 of 2016).	Legislation	Central Government	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of mangroves explicitly.
Forest (Conservation) Rules, 2022.	Regulation	Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of mangroves explicitly.
Green Credit Rules, 2023	Regulation	Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Carbon credits could be extended to seagrass and saltmarsh habitats.
The Biological Diversity Act, 2002	Legislation/Act	The National Biodiversity Authority (NBA)	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of blue carbon ecosystems explicitly.
Biological Diversity Rules, 2004.	Regulation	Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of blue carbon ecosystems explicitly.
The Wild Life Protection Act, 1972 (WLPA)	Legislation	Central Government	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of blue carbon ecosystems explicitly.
Wetlands (Conservation and Management) Rules 2017	Regulation	Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N				Recognise the benefits of blue carbon ecosystems explicitly.
Order No. 30035/15/97-Fy (T-1) Vol. V on restrictions in marine fishing activities.	Regulation	Ministry of Fisheries, Animal Husbandry and Dairying, Department of Fisheries	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant. One time order specific to COVID-19

Notification of the Ministry of Environment and Forests regarding coastal zone regulation.	Regulation	Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change, Department of Environment, Forests and Wildlife	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y				Not relevant - notification
Circular Concerning Joint Forest Management (No. 6-21/89-P.P).	Miscellaneous	Government of India Ministry of Environment and Forests Department of Environment, Forests and Wildlife	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Potentially those mangrove habitats that are categorised as forests
STATE LEGISLATION															
Title	Type	Responsible entity	MG	SM	SG	W *	A	M	B	ES	A	M	B	Opportunity	
State Action Plan on Climate Change For Andhra Pradesh, 2012	Policy	Government of Andhra Pradesh	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N				Expand to seagrass and saltmarsh ecosystems.	
Sustainable Development Goals 2030: Strategies and Action plan for Karnataka, 2020.	Policy	Government of Karnataka	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	Y				Expand to seagrass and saltmarsh ecosystems, and include mitigation benefits under SDG13 Climate Action	
Tamil Nadu: Tamil Nadu State Environment Policy 2017.	Policy	Government of Tamil Nadu, Department of Environment	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	N				Explicitly recognise the benefits of blue carbon ecosystems.	
West Bengal Fisheries Policy, 2015	Policy	Government of West Bengal, Department of Fisheries	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Conservation and protection of blue carbon ecosystems will be beneficial to the fisheries sector and livelihoods.	
Kerala State Environment Policy, 2009.	Policy	Government of Kerala, Department of Environment	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	Y				Expand to seagrass and saltmarsh ecosystems.	
Tamil Nadu Aquaculture (Regulation) Act, 1995 (Act 6 of 1995).	Legislation	Government of Tamil Nadu	Y	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N				Expand to seagrass and saltmarsh ecosystems.	

Andhra Pradesh Forest Act, 1967	Legislation	Government of Andhra Pradesh	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include mangroves explicitly as some of them can be classified as reserved forests and not wetlands
Kerala Forest Act, 1961 (No. 4 of 1962).	Legislation	Government of Kerala	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include mangroves explicitly as some of them can be classified as reserved forests and not wetlands
Orissa Forest Act, 1972 (Act No. 14 of 1972).	Legislation	Government of Odisha	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include mangroves explicitly as some of them can be classified as reserved forests and not wetlands
Karnataka Forest Act, 1963 (No. 5 of 1964).	Legislation	Government of Karnataka	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include mangroves explicitly as some of them can be classified as reserved forests and not wetlands
Andhra Pradesh Marine Fishing (Regulation) Act, 1995 (Act No. 9 of 1995).	Legislation	Government of Andhra Pradesh	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include protection of seagrass habitats.
Tamil Nadu Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1983 (Act No. 8 of 1983).	Legislation	Government of Tamil Nadu	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include protection of seagrass habitats.
Orissa Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1981 (Act No. 10 of 1982).	Legislation	Government of Odisha	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include protection of seagrass habitats.
Maharashtra Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1981 (Act No. LIV of 1981).	Legislation	Government of Maharashtra	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include protection of seagrass habitats.
Goa Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Act, 2019 (Goa Act No. 72 of 2019).	Legislation	Government of Goa	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant – amendment

Tamil Nadu Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Amendment Act, 2017 (Act No. 31 of 2017).	Legislation	Government of Tamil Nadu	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - amendment
Goa Marine Fishing Regulation (Relaxation of Time Limit for Registration of Vessels) Act, 2002 (Goa Act No. 10 of 2002).	Legislation	Government of Goa	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - An Act to relax the time limit for registration of vessels under the Goa, Daman and Diu Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1980
West Bengal Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1993 (Act No. IX of 1993).	Legislation	Government of West Bengal	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include protection of seagrass habitats.
Karnataka Marine Fishing (Regulation) Act (No. 24 of 1986).	Legislation	Government of Karnataka	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include protection of seagrass habitats.
Goa, Daman and Diu Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1981.	Legislation	Government of Goa, Daman and Diu	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include protection of seagrass habitats.
Kerala Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1980 (Act No. 10 of 1981).	Legislation	Government of Kerala	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include protection of seagrass habitats.
Kerala Marine Fishing Regulation Rules, 2018.	Regulation	Government of Kerala	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - details fishing vessels and licences
Order concerning the West Bengal Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1993 (Order No. 3209-Fish/C-V/1A-2/90 Pt. I).	Regulation	Government of West Bengal	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - one time order to specify mesh size
West Bengal Marine Fishing Regulation Rules, 1995.	Regulation	Government of West Bengal	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - details fishing vessels and licences
Andhra Pradesh Marine Fishing (Regulation) Rules, 1995.	Regulation	Government of Andhra Pradesh	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - details fishing vessels and licences
Karnataka Marine Fishing Regulation Rules, 1987 (No. 24 of 1987).	Regulation	Government of Karnataka	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - details fishing vessels and licences

Orissa Marine Fishing Regulation Rules, 1983.	Regulation	Government of Odisha	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - details fishing vessels and licences
Goa, Daman and Diu Marine Fishing Regulations, 1982.	Regulation	Government of Goa, Daman and Diu	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - details fishing vessels and licences
Order of 25 March 2020 regulating fishing activities in marine and inland fisheries districts for strict compliance.	Regulation	Government of Kerala	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - one time order specific to COVID-19
Rules No. SRO A-15(c)/2015 amending Tamil Nadu Marine Fishing Regulation Rules, 1983.	Regulation	Government of Tamil Nadu	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - amendment
Lakshadweep Marine Fishing Regulation, 2000.	Regulation	Administration of the Union territory of Lakshadweep	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include protection of seagrass habitats.
Notification No. 3211-Fish/C-V concerning the West Bengal Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1993.	Regulation	Government of West Bengal	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - notification
Notification No. 3216-Fish/C-V concerning the West Bengal Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1993.	Regulation	Government of West Bengal	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - notification
Order concerning the Maharashtra Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1981	Order	Government of Maharashtra	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - specific order
Maharashtra Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Ordinance, 2021.	Legislation	Government of Maharashtra	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant – amendment
Kerala Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Act, 2021 (Act No. 17 of 2021).	Legislation	Government of Kerala	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - amendment

Kerala Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Act, 1986 (Act No. 8 of 1986).	Legislation	Government of Kerala	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - amendment
Orissa Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Rules, 2005.	Regulation	Government of Odisha	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - amendment
West Bengal Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Rules, 1998.	Regulation	Government of West Bengal	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - amendment
Gujarat Fisheries Act, 2003 (Act No. 8 of 2003).	Legislation	Government of Gujarat	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include protection of seagrass habitats.
Andhra Pradesh Forest Act, 1967	Legislation	Government of Andhra Pradesh	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include mangroves explicitly as some of them can be classified as protected forests and not wetlands
Kerala Forest Act, 1961 (No. 4 of 1962).	Legislation	Government of Kerala	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include mangroves explicitly as some of them can be classified as reserved forests and not wetlands
Odisha Forest Development (Tax on sale of forest produce by Government or Odisha Forest Development Corporation) (Repeal) Act, 2017.	Legislation	Government of Kerala	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - repeal of Odisha Act 18, 2003
Kerala Promotion of Tree Growth in Non-Forest Areas Act, 2005 (Act No. 46 of 2005).	Legislation	Government of Kerala	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - this Act promotes afforestation for commercial use of timber alongside increasing green cover and biodiversity
Kerala Promotion of Tree Growth in Non-Forest Areas (Amendment) Act, 2007 (Act No. 19 of 2007).	Legislation	Government of Kerala	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - amendment

Andhra Pradesh Forest Produce (Fixation of Selling Prices) Act, 1989 (Act. No. 29 of 1989).	Legislation	Government of Andhra Pradesh	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - Act to provide for the supply of forest produce and the fixation of selling price in respect therefor and the constitution of an industrial plantation fund and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto.
Orissa Forest Produce (Control of Trade) Act, 1981 (Act No. 22 of 1981).	Legislation	Government of Odisha	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - does not cover mangrove tree species.
Gujarat Minor Forest Produce Trade Nationalisation Act, 1979 (No. 7 of 1979).	Legislation	Government of Gujarat	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - does not include mangrove tree species.
Maharashtra Private Forest (Acquisition) Act 1975	Legislation	Government of Maharashtra	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Potentially if the privately owned mangroves are designated as forests and not wetlands.
Gujarat Private forests (Acquisition) Act, 1972 (Act No. 14 of 1973).	Legislation	Government of Gujarat	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Potentially if the privately owned mangroves are designated as forests and not wetlands.
Orissa Forest Act, 1972 (Act No. 14 of 1972).	Legislation	Government of Odisha	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include mangroves explicitly as some of them can be classified as reserved forests and not wetlands
Kerala Private Forests (Vesting and Assignment) Act, 1971 (Act No. 26 of 1971).	Legislation	Government of Kerala	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - refers to agricultural land
Andhra Pradesh Minor Forest Produce (Regulation of Trade) Act, 1971 (Act No. 4 of 1971).	Legislation	Government of Andhra Pradesh	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - minor forest produce does not include mangrove trees or any of their parts
Maharashtra Minor Forest Produce (Regulation of Trade) Act, 1969 (Act No. 57 of 1969).	Legislation	Government of Maharashtra	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - minor forest produce does not include mangrove trees or any of their parts

Karnataka Forest Act, 1963 (No. 5 of 1964).	Legislation	Government of Karnataka	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include mangroves explicitly as some of them can be classified as reserved forests and not wetlands
Tamil Nadu Private Forests (Assumption of Management) Act, 1961 (No. 55 of 1961).	Legislation	Government of Tamil Nadu	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Potentially if the privately owned mangroves are designated as forests and not wetlands
West Bengal Private Forests Act, 1948 (No. 14 of 1948).	Legislation	Government of West Bengal	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Potentially if the privately owned mangroves are designated as forests and not wetlands.
Tamil Nadu Forest Act, 1882 (No. 5 of 1882).	Legislation	Tamil Nadu	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include mangroves explicitly as some of them can be classified as reserved forests and not wetlands
Orissa Village Forests Rules, 1985	Regulation	Odisha	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Mangroves are unlikely to be village forests, but this would need more assessment to understand the context and possibilities
Orissa Forest (Detection, Enquiry and Disposal of Forest Offence) Rules, 1980.	Regulation	Government of Odisha	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				This does not include the definition of forest; thus mangroves should be included in the Orissa Forest Act 1972 instead of these Rules
Karnataka Forest Rules, 1969.	Regulation	Government of Karnataka	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Include mangroves explicitly as some of them can be classified as reserved forests and not wetlands
Maharashtra Forest Rule 2014	Regulation	Government of Maharashtra	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Mangroves are included in the tree list.
Bombay Forest Rules, 1942	Regulation	Government of Maharashtra	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Describes the activities in protected forests - mangroves can be protected forests and there are mangroves in Mumbai area.
Karnataka Forest Code, 1976.	Code	Government of Karnataka	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - regulates elephants

Andhra Pradesh Forest (Amendment) Act, 2016 (Act No. 15 of 2016).	Legislation	Government of Andhra Pradesh	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - amendment
Kerala Forest (Amendment) Act, 2010 (Act No. 8 of 2010).	Legislation	Government of Kerala	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N				Not relevant - amendment

* In a general sense - may include inland wetlands

** The inclusion depends on the version of the NDC or INDC

Annex B: List of Policies and Legislation

National Environment Policy, 2006.

India's Long-Term Low-Carbon Development Strategy, 2022.

National Disaster Management Plan, 2019

National Policy on Marine Fisheries, 2017.

National Wildlife Action Plan, 2017

Bay of Bengal Large Marine Ecosystem Strategic Action Programme, 2015

National Agroforestry Policy, 2014

Comprehensive Marine Fishing Policy 2004.

National Forest Policy, 1988.

Environment (Protection) Act, 1986 (No. 29 of 1986).

Environment (Protection) Rules, 1986.

Environmental Impact Assessment Notification, 2006.

The Coastal Regulation Zone Notification, 1991

Notification S.O. 4886(E) of 2021 amending the Coastal Regulation Zone Notification, 2019.

Island Coastal Regulation Zone Notification, 2019.

The Coastal Aquaculture Authority Act, 2005 (Act No. 24 of 2005).

Coastal Aquaculture Authority Rules, 2024.

Indian Forest Act, 1927.

The Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980

Compensatory Afforestation Fund Act, 2016 (Act No. 38 of 2016).

Forest (Conservation) Rules, 2022.

Green Credit Rules, 2023

The Biological Diversity Act, 2002

Biological Diversity Rules, 2004.

The Wild Life Protection Act, 1972

Wetlands (Conservation and Management) Rules, 2017

Order No. 30035/15/97-Fy (T-1) Vol. V on restrictions in marine fishing activities.

Notification of the Ministry of Environment and Forests regarding coastal zone regulation.

Circular Concerning Joint Forest Management (No. 6-21/89-P.P).

State Action Plan on Climate Change For Andhra Pradesh, 2012

Sustainable Development Goals 2030: Strategies and Action plan for Karnataka, 2020.

Tamil Nadu: Tamil Nadu State Environment Policy 2017.

West Bengal Fisheries Policy, 2015

Kerala State Environment Policy, 2009.

Tamil Nadu Aquaculture (Regulation) Act, 1995 (Act 6 of 1995).

Andhra Pradesh Forest Act, 1967

Kerala Forest Act, 1961 (No. 4 of 1962).

Orissa Forest Act, 1972 (Act No. 14 of 1972).

Karnataka Forest Act, 1963 (No. 5 of 1964).

Andhra Pradesh Marine Fishing (Regulation) Act, 1995 (Act No. 9 of 1995).

Tamil Nadu Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1983 (Act No. 8 of 1983).

Orissa Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1981 (Act No. 10 of 1982).

Maharashtra Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1981 (Act No. LIV of 1981).

Goa Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Act, 2019 (Goa Act No. 72 of 2019).

Tamil Nadu Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Amendment Act, 2017 (Act No. 31 of 2017).

Goa Marine Fishing Regulation (Relaxation of Time Limit for Registration of Vessels) Act, 2002 (Goa Act No. 10 of 2002).

West Bengal Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1993 (Act No. IX of 1993).

Karnataka Marine Fishing (Regulation) Act (No. 24 of 1986).

Goa, Daman and Diu Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1981.

Kerala Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1980 (Act No. 10 of 1981).

Kerala Marine Fishing Regulation Rules, 2018.

Order concerning the West Bengal Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1993 (Order No. 3209-Fish/C-V/1A-2/90 Pt. I).

West Bengal Marine Fishing Regulation Rules, 1995.

Andhra Pradesh Marine Fishing (Regulation) Rules, 1995.

Karnataka Marine Fishing Regulation Rules, 1987 (No. 24 of 1987).

Orissa Marine Fishing Regulation Rules, 1983.

Goa, Daman and Diu Marine Fishing Regulations, 1982.

Order of 25 March 2020 regulating fishing activities in marine and inland fisheries districts for strict compliance.

Rules No. SRO A-15(c)/2015 amending Tamil Nadu Marine Fishing Regulation Rules, 1983.

Lakshadweep Marine Fishing Regulation, 2000.

Notification No. 3211-Fish/C-V concerning the West Bengal Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1993.

Notification No. 3216-Fish/C-V concerning the West Bengal Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1993.

Order concerning the Maharashtra Marine Fishing Regulation Act, 1981

Maharashtra Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Ordinance, 2021.

Kerala Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Act, 2021 (Act No. 17 of 2021).

Kerala Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Act, 1986 (Act No. 8 of 1986).

Orissa Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Rules, 2005.

West Bengal Marine Fishing Regulation (Amendment) Rules, 1998.

Gujarat Fisheries Act, 2003 (Act No. 8 of 2003).

Andhra Pradesh Forest Act, 1967

Kerala Forest Act, 1961 (No. 4 of 1962).

Odisha Forest Development (Tax on sale of forest produce by Government or Odisha Forest Development Corporation) (Repeal) Act, 2017.

Kerala Promotion of Tree Growth in Non-Forest Areas Act, 2005 (Act No. 46 of 2005).

Kerala Promotion of Tree Growth in Non-Forest Areas (Amendment) Act, 2007 (Act No. 19 of 2007).

Andhra Pradesh Forest Produce (Fixation of Selling Prices) Act, 1989 (Act. No. 29 of 1989).

Orissa Forest Produce (Control of Trade) Act, 1981 (Act No. 22 of 1981).

Gujarat Minor Forest Produce Trade Nationalisation Act, 1979 (No. 7 of 1979).

Maharashtra Private Forest (Acquisition) Act 1975

Gujarat Private forests (Acquisition) Act, 1972 (Act No. 14 of 1973).

Orissa Forest Act, 1972 (Act No. 14 of 1972).

Kerala Private Forests (Vesting and Assignment) Act, 1971 (Act No. 26 of 1971).

Andhra Pradesh Minor Forest Produce (Regulation of Trade) Act, 1971 (Act No. 4 of 1971).

Maharashtra Minor Forest Produce (Regulation of Trade) Act, 1969 (Act No. 57 of 1969).

Karnataka Forest Act, 1963 (No. 5 of 1964).

Tamil Nadu Private Forests (Assumption of Management) Act, 1961 (No. 55 of 1961).

West Bengal Private Forests Act, 1948 (No. 14 of 1948).

Tamil Nadu Forest Act, 1882 (No. 5 of 1882)

Orissa Village Forests Rules, 1985

Orissa Forest (Detection, Enquiry and Disposal of Forest Offence) Rules, 1980.

Karnataka Forest Rules, 1969.

Maharashtra Forest Rule 2014

Bombay Forest Rules, 1942

Karnataka Forest Code, 1976.

Andhra Pradesh Forest (Amendment) Act, 2016 (Act No. 15 of 2016).

Kerala Forest (Amendment) Act, 2010 (Act No. 8 of 2010).